

Four Dimensions of Structural Empowerment, Job Satisfaction, and Their Associations with
Turnover Intentions Among Certified Nursing Assistants Employed in U.S. Nursing Homes in
2004

A Dissertation

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Abstract

Background: With the increasing demands for long-term care, it is critical for attention to be given to the recruitment and retention of direct care workers who are at the frontline of healthcare. Retention issues and increased turnover rates pose a significant economic and decrease the quality of patient care.

Purpose: This quantitative, correlational study aimed to examine (1) participants' level of structural empowerment; (2) the relationships between variables: structural empowerment, job satisfaction, and turnover intention; (3) the significance of variables predicting turnover intention, and (4) significant differences in structural empowerment and job satisfaction predicting turnover intention when grouped by age and citizenship.

Design: Kanter's structural empowerment theory provided the framework for this observational study, using archival data from the 2004 National Nursing Assistant Survey (NNAS) data. The sample population for this study included 2,064 participants. Binary logistic regressions were performed to examine the perceptions of structural empowerment between two turnover intention groups.

Results: Moderate levels of structural empowerment were perceived as overall structural empowerment ($M = 12.57$). Using binary logistic regression models based on an α level of .05, significant relationships were found between opportunity ($B = -0.86$, $OR = 0.42$, $p < .001$), support ($B = -0.71$, $OR = 0.49$, $p < .001$), and information ($B = -0.57$, $OR = 0.57$, $p < .001$). The resources subscale of structural empowerment was the only subdimension that was not a significant predictor of turnover intention. However, this did not impact the significant predictive outcomes between structural empowerment ($B = -0.12$, $OR = 0.89$, $p < .001$), and job satisfaction ($B = -.97$, $OR = 0.38$, $p < .001$) on the yes category of turnover intention.

Conclusion: Structural empowerment and job satisfaction were found to be predictors of the CNAs' turnover intention. These findings support Kanter's structural empowerment theory, the framework used to guide this study.

Preface

I would like to dedicate the doctoral study to the many dedicated, certified nursing assistants who continue to work in our healthcare systems, assisted living, and home health care. During the COVID-19 pandemic, many of you selflessly made the necessary adjustments at a moment's notice to provide quality care continuity. You are an essential part of our frontline and one of many unsung heroes. Your efforts and dedication are greatly appreciated and celebrated.

Acknowledgments

First, I would like to give all the honor and glory to God, my Alpha, and Omega, my extraordinary omniscience, omnipresent, and omniscient Counselor. I kept my faith and finished the course. I could not have completed this long and tedious journey without you. I want to extend my most heartfelt thank you to all my family, friends, and colleagues who have supported me throughout this journey. I would also like to thank my dear and good friend, who is more like a big-little sister, Dr. Darrlyn Cornelius-Averhart.

I would be remiss if I did not acknowledge and thank my devoted and supportive committee members: Dr. Carlos Cardillo, Dr. Ryan Dwight, and Dr. Oestmann. To Dr. Cardillo, I am finally Phinished! My journey would not have been possible without your expertise and leadership.

To the many dedicated CNAs worldwide, who work tirelessly in various capacities and facilities or in-home health care settings, thank you for all you have done and continue to do.

Dedication

This doctoral study is dedicated to all my family and friends who have supported me throughout this process; those that asked, even when they may not have wanted, those that listened when they may not have liked, and those that prayed when they needed.

To my children, Macy, Jr., Macayla, and Christian, I pray that I have achieved my goal of leading by example and being a positive role model for you all. You all have such bright futures, and I am honored and humbled to be your mom. Go forth and continue to do great things! I will be in the background cheering you on.

To the beautiful lady who saw my potential in hiring me for my first position at CDC, my dearest friend, and mentor, Sabrina Harper. If it wasn't for you, I would not be at this point in my career. You provided me with opportunities that fueled my imagination and inspired my thirst for knowledge and to remove self-limiting beliefs. I can't thank you enough.

To my rock and late mother, Lanitha, my late father, Ricardo, my greatest love and inspiration, my late grandmother, Lillian, my protector and provider, my late grandfathers Booker T. and Harry, and one of my greatest inspirations inspiring me to not settle for less, to commit my life as a civil servant, the late great-grandfather, Daddy Bill. You all have always been my biggest fan, and this chapter in my life has been no different. I wish you all were here to see this accomplishment. I know you are here in spirit. I love and miss you all immensely.

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Chapter I: Introduction to the Study

Over the years, the recruitment and retention of U.S. nursing assistants working in the long-term care industry have been studied considerably (Barbarotta, 2010; Berridge et al., 2018; Culp et al., 2008; Gion, 2019; Rosen et al., 2011; Stone et al., 2017). Significant turnover intention rates and constant challenges in the recruitment and retention of direct care workers have fueled enduring concerns of experts and policymakers about the capacity of the long-term care workforce's supply of direct service workers (DSWs) to meet the increasing demands for Long-Term Care (LTC) services. By 2030, people aged 65 and over will make up one-fifth of the U.S. population (U.S. Government Accountability Office, 2016). For policymakers and administrators, this news is alarming.

After 2010, the United States (U.S.) has seen an increase in demand for direct care workers in long-term care environments (Bureau of Labor Statistics & Department of Labor, 2022; Khatutsky et al., 2010; The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018; Leiter et al., 2011; Paraprofessional Healthcare Institute, 2018; & U.S. Department of Labor, 2014). By 2030, the demand for CNAs has projected to increase due to the number of baby boomers reaching the age of 65 (Alshutwi, 2017; Bureau of Labor Statistics & Decker et al., 2009; Department of Labor, 2022; The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018; Leiter et al., 2011; Squillace et al., 2007; Stearns & D'Arcy, 2008; United States Government Accountability Office, 2016). The growth pace of the boomers is one of the most significant demographic trends in U.S. history (Carrington College Blog, 2014; Dill et al., 2013; Knickman & Snell, 2002; Squillace et al., 2007). With the

American life expectancy rate rise, the U.S. healthcare system will see increasing demands from its aging population. With these demands comes increased employment opportunities for direct care workers, expected to exceed the vacancy rates of other U.S. job industries. Long-term care facilities, such as nursing homes, will soon become home to millions of baby boomers over the next several decades. This anticipated rise in demand creates challenges for long-term care facilities. Currently, health care administrators are not able to retain Certified Nursing Assistants (CNAs), the essential frontline workers of health care infrastructures (Mather et al., 2015; Patel et al., 2014; Rosen et al., 2011; Stearns & D'Arcy, 2008).

According to the Office of the Assistant Secretary for Planning and Evaluation (ASPE), the United States (U.S.) has seen the demand for direct care workers in long-term care environments after the year 2010 increase significantly (The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018; Khatutsky et al., 2011; Paraprofessional Healthcare Institute, 2018; U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2022). It is projected that by 2030, the demand for these essential workers will see a substantial increase as the baby boomer generation continues to age and require long-term care (Bureau of Labor Statistics & Department of Labor, 2022; Decker et al., 2009; Leiter et al., 2011; Squillace et al., 2008; Stearns & D'Arcy, 2008; U.S. Government Accountability Office, 2016). The growth pace of the boomers is one of the most significant demographic trends in U.S. history (Mather et al., 2015; Squillace et al., 2008). Long-term care facilities, such as nursing homes, will soon become home to millions of baby boomers over the next several decades. An increase in demand will create challenges for long-term care facilities currently not able to retain

Certified Nursing Assistants (CNAs), the frontline workers of health care infrastructures (Berridge et al., 2020; & Mather et al., 2015).

In late February of 2020, the United States rapidly saw cases of COVID-19 spread inside a nursing home in Seattle, WA. Within a week, over 70 out of 170 members of the staff were out sick with COVID-19-like symptoms (Baker, 2020; McMichael et al., 2020). Across the country in North Carolina (N.C.), a recent N.C. Health News report found short staffing at over three-quarters of the 19 N.C. nursing homes identified through public records or media sources as experiencing COVID-19 outbreaks (Goldsmith, 2020).

With these demands, increased employment opportunities for direct care workers may exceed the rates of other U.S. job industries. CNAs provide 80 to 90 percent of direct patient care and are the backbone of U.S. long-term care industries (The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018; PHI, 2020; Sloane et al., 2010). Employment growth rates for direct care workers may increase by 23.8 percent (Frogner, 2015). Between 2016 and 2060, adults aged 65 and older may double, rising from 49 to 95 million (Paraprofessional Healthcare Institute, 2018). Adults between 18 and 64 will only increase by 14 percent (Paraprofessional Healthcare Institute, 2018).

Background of Study

With the Baby-Boomer population aging and retiring, there is great concern as the future availability of direct care workers does not look promising to meet the additional needs for long-term care (Matthews et al., 2018). These workers together create a critical core workforce that will provide personal care, supervision, and emotional support to millions of elderly and disabled

clients. Often, these workers receive low wages and lack training and growth opportunities, considering the care they provide. Wage inequality, unpaid leave, stressful working conditions, long hours, racism/discrimination, and high turnover rates are among the many issues that plagued this stigmatized or prejudged health care worker sector. An analysis of the NNAS in a study revealed that dissatisfaction with low wages was expected and linked to overall job dissatisfaction (Rakovski & Price-Glynn, 2010).

According to the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, employment of nursing assistants may increase 9 percent between 2018 and 2028, revealing them as the fastest-growing occupation in the (Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2022). At 38%, nursing care facilities are the largest employer of nursing assistants, with hospitals employing 27 % of nursing assistants, continuing care facilities, 11%, home healthcare services employing five percent, and four percent employed by the Government (Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2022). The day-to-day work routine for nursing assistants can be tedious and lengthy. Often, they must spend the bulk of their day on their feet taking care of their patients or residents. Out of all occupations, nursing assistants have the highest rates of injuries and illnesses (Bureau of Labor Statistics & Department of Labor, 2022; Walton & Rogers, 2017).

In his book, "Who Will Care for Us: Long-term Care and the Long-Term Workforce," Paul Osterman revealed that by 2030, the U.S. would be facing a shortage of 151,000 paid direct care workers and 3.8 million unpaid family caregivers (Osterman, 2017). He further indicates that by 2040, the deficit will be much more substantial, with the U.S. possibly facing a shortage

of 355,000 paid workers and 11 million unpaid family caregivers (Osterman, 2017). Citing U.S. Census statistics, Osterman (2017) stated that in 2015, 18 percent of U.S. CNAs and 27 percent of home care aides were immigrants. However, Osterman offers a glimmer of hope. He indicated that more workers would become attracted to this occupation if workers were respected and received more training. With the restructuring in the complexity of the U.S. health care delivery system, CNAs would feel empowered and find this work meaningful, which will help minimize the risk for turnover.

With the Baby-Boomer population aging and retiring, there is great concern as the future availability of direct care workers does not look promising to meet the additional needs for long-term care (Haddad et al., 2020; Matthews et al., 2018). These workers together create a critical core workforce that will provide personal care, supervision, and emotional support to millions of elderly and disabled clients. Often, these workers receive low wages or are subjected to inappropriate treatment, considering the care they provide. Wage inequality, unpaid leave, stressful working conditions, long hours, racism/discrimination, and high turnover rates are among the many issues that plagued this stigmatized or prejudged health care worker sector. An analysis of the NNAS in a study revealed dissatisfaction with low wages to be expected and linked with overall job dissatisfaction (Rakovski & Price-Glynn, 2010).

Empowerment-focused recruitment practices are methods to improve CNA job satisfaction and retention. Few studies have associated an assortment of empowerment styles with job satisfaction, intent to stay, and lower turnover (Berridge et al., 2018; Brannon, 2010;

Chunfeng & Zhou, 2009; Hauck et al., 2011; Laschinger et al., 2004; Rosen et al., 2011).

Practices frequently related to staff empowerment involved delivering more significant opportunities and expanding more supportive organizational values. In a survey research sample of 3,039 direct care workers, Kiefer et al. (2005) found intent to leave to be positively related to perceived lack of opportunity. Similarly, Probst et al. (2010) conducted research based on a nationally representative sample of nursing homes and 2,897 CNAs. Their results indicated a positive association between job satisfaction and organizational climate, supervisor behavior, sufficient time for tasks, value, and hourly earnings. In a mixed-methods research study, Yeatts & Cready's (2007) findings indicated that CNAs were most likely to produce modest positive outcomes in CNA empowerment, increased job performance and job satisfaction, and provided better patient quality care when organizations used an empowered work teams approach. In addition, they found that CNAs who experienced these work cultures encompassed workgroups that had a lower likelihood of leaving or being fired (Yeatts & Cready, 2007).

Recruitment and retention strategies often stress the importance of having positive work environments conducive to offering support to CNAs to maintain a supply that can meet their demands. Identifying ways to attract and retain immigrant direct care workers can afford opportunities that will contribute to the success of long and fulfilling careers for direct care workers when studies assist by contributing to the literature.

Problem Statement

1.5 million nursing assistants work in the U.S. healthcare system (Staff Writers, 2020). While the majority are helping fill critical roles in nursing care facilities, others are working with home healthcare agencies, hospitals, and assisted living facilities. As the demand for direct care workers in nursing homes continues to rise, greater attention and effort must identify sources to meet the needs of the industry (The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018). The poor quality of nursing assistant jobs enables the ability of nursing homes to recruit and retain enough CNAs to meet the demand. However, to do so, they require working conditions and environments conducive to retaining them. Therefore, efforts to increase direct care workforce stability should address these concerns.

Knowledge Gap

Despite having a significant reliance on utilizing nursing assistants to fill vital health care jobs across the U.S., the research knowledgebase lacks studies that investigated the relationships between structural empowerment and turnover intention among migrant certified nursing assistants (de Castro et al., 2008; Henrici, 2013; Khatutsky et al., 2010; Ko et al., 2015; Sloane et al., 2010). Considering the number of non-U.S. citizens occupying nursing assistant positions in the healthcare industry, this population continues to receive little attention in nursing research (Ko, et al., 2015). While there are studies on nurse empowerment and turnover intention, there are gaps in the literature studying relationships between citizenship status, structural empowerment, and turnover intention. Therefore, this study aimed to examine these constructs

among nursing assistants who work in U.S. nursing homes. This study will aid by informing healthcare administrators, nursing admins, and other skilled nursing facility leaders about the vitality of offering an effective work environment conducive to the retention of nursing assistants.

Chapter one of this study offers background information on the relationship between structural empowerment and nursing assistant turnover intention. This chapter provides the research problem and purpose for this study, defines research concepts, and reveals the research questions this study will answer. These findings will contribute additional knowledge to the literature base to assist policymakers, senior leadership, direct supervisors, and most importantly, certified nursing assistants, the essential frontline workers. They provide our elderly populations with the assistance and care they need daily.

Purpose of Study

The purpose of this observational study is to examine the relationships between structural empowerment, its four subscales (access to opportunity, support, information, and resources), job satisfaction, and turnover intention in U.S. and non-U.S. citizen CNAs, analyzing data from the 2004 National Nursing Assistant Survey (NNAS). In addition, this study aimed to contribute to the knowledge base by understanding how CNAs employed in skilled nursing facilities and work environments affect their turnover intention. CNAs' perception of feeling unappreciated and unsupported in their work environments contributes significantly to their turnover (Bowers et al., 2003). Factors like job satisfaction and intent to stay among nursing assistants have been studied

consistently in long-term care facilities (Bishop et al., 2009; Bowers et al., 2003; Castle, 2006; Dill, et al., 2013; Noelker et al., 2006).

According to Kanter's theoretical framework, this study explored the relationships between the four dimensions of structural empowerment (access to opportunity, resources, information, and support), citizenship status, and turnover intention in certified nursing assistants working in U.S. nursing homes. This research will aid nursing home administrators, policymakers, and educators, in offering an effective working environment conducive to not only the recruitment of certified nursing assistants but to retaining them.

Nature of Study

This research used a quantitative approach based upon a descriptive correlation non-experimental design. The study used correlational statistics techniques to study the relationships between structural empowerment, job satisfaction, and turnover intention while examining whether age or citizenship status affected these relationships. Quantitative research tests a theory describing, analyzing relationships, and determining cause and effect connections between variables (Grove & Gray, p. 16, 2019). Quantitative methods and a non-experimental research design will help the study's planning, construction, implementation, and analysis. A rigorous quantitative survey contains the appropriate measuring instruments, accurate sample population representation, and a tightly managed research design.

Kanter's Structural Empowerment theory guided the study, this proposed research aimed to determine: (1) the relationships among the subscales of structural empowerment and turnover

intention among certified nursing assistants. Kanter's (1993) theory of structural empowerment provided the theoretical framework for examining the relationship between structural empowerment, citizenship status, and turnover intention in CNAs working in U.S. nursing homes. In her structural theory of structural empowerment, Kanter asserts that formal and informal systemic structures are the sources of workplace empowerment (Kluska et al., 2004).

Significance of Study

Turnover rates for CNAs have remained elevated over many decades. They have often exceeded 100% for CNAs, the frontline and most common type of caregiver found in nursing homes (Institute of Medicine, 2008). The turnover rate among nursing aides within the long-term care direct-care workers experiences high levels of turnover and job satisfaction due to low wages, poor working environments, high rates of work-related injuries, and low opportunities for career advancement (Institute of Medicine, 2008). These high rates have continued, despite the significant number of studies documenting relationships between turnover in nursing homes and poor quality of care (Castle et al., 2006) conducted by concerned scholars and policymakers.

Recruiting and retaining CNAs in the United States, who work in long-term care facilities, has been the focus of several studies over the years (Berridge et al., 2018; Castle et al., 2007; Donohue, 2009; Rosen et al., 2011). Across the U.S., the high turnover rate among nursing assistants in long-term care facilities continues to be a significant workforce issue. Excessive turnover rates and low nursing assistant retention harm patients' quality of care and have a substantial financial impact on long-term care facilities. Employee turnover is a costly and

reoccurring challenge in many nursing homes and assisted living facilities. The American Association of Homes and Services for the Aging reported in 2007 reported the annual costs for CNAs' turnover to be an estimated \$4 billion (Sloane et al., 2010).

Acker et al. (2015) revealed in their study that not only are foreign-born direct care workers in U.S. nursing facilities not a risk to nursing facilities' quality ratings; they perhaps are connected to nursing facilities' enhanced performance. Nonetheless, nursing homes may face ongoing challenges as they try to appeal to a significant and qualified recruit pool, presenting them with low salaries, meager benefits, and unappealing work environments. As Medicaid continues to increase coverage to offer access to long-term care for a larger aging population, policymakers and administrators may want to contemplate methods by which they can strategically recruit and retain workers (Cicolini et al., 2013).

Research Questions

Based upon the limited existing research on certified nursing assistants and the few published studies that examined the relationships between their structural empowerment and turnover intention, the following research questions were examined:

Based upon the limited existing research on certified nursing assistants and the few published studies that examined the relationships between their structural empowerment and turnover intention, the following research questions were examined:

Research Question 1: Does access to opportunity significantly predict CNA turnover intention?

Research Question 2: Does access to support significantly predict CNA turnover intention?

Research Question 3: Does access to information significantly predict CNA turnover intention?

Research Question 4: Does access to resources significantly predict CNA turnover intention?

Research Question 5: Do structural empowerment and job satisfaction significantly predict turnover intention?

Research Question 5a: Controlling for age, do structural empowerment significantly predict turnover intention?

Research Question 5b: Controlling for citizenship status, do structural empowerment significantly predict turnover intention?

Definition of Key Terms

To understand the meaning of the concepts involved in this study. It is necessary to be familiar with the research's terms:

Certified Nursing Assistants (CNAs). Assistants working in nursing homes who 1) provide support to nursing home patients with their activities of daily living (ADL), 2) are financially compensated to offer their services, 3) are certified to provide Medicare/Medicaid reimbursable services; 4) worked at least 16 hours per week 5) are nursing home employees; not

contract employees and 6) has completed a federally required, minimum of 75 hours of state-approved training and has passed a competency evaluation (Khatutsky et al., 2011).

Citizenship status. In this study, citizenship refers to individuals geographically belonging to or related to a particular land, characterized by continuity, persistence, flexibility, and good relations with others (Al-Sabeelah et al., 2015).

Direct Care Workers (DCWs). Includes nursing assistants (NAs), home health and home care aides, personal care workers, and personal care attendants who provide hands-on care with essential daily tasks (bathing, assistance with getting dressed, and help with other assisted daily living tasks) and other caring labor duties to their clients with various illness and disabilities (Kiefer et al., 2005). The Pennsylvania Long-Term Care Council and its committees define "direct care workers" as paid frontline workers who offer hands-on care, services, and support to elderly patients and patients with disabilities who are not elderly (Pennsylvania Long-Term Care Council, 2019). In this study, direct care workers refer to certified nursing assistants (CNAs) working in nursing facilities eligible to participate in the National Nursing Assistant Survey (Khatutsky et al., 2010).

Job Satisfaction. In their systematic review, Squires et al., (2015) defined job satisfaction using the traditional job satisfaction model, which focuses on the effective alignment of an employee toward their work. Stamps explained job satisfaction as "the extent to which people like their jobs" (p. 13). Locke (1969), job satisfaction and dissatisfaction are complex emotional reactions to the job. He goes further to explain three natural emotions tied to this

construct: a) cognition, the documentation of existents, b) evaluation, the estimate of the perceived benefits or harm experienced in the relationship, and c) the regulation of action (Locke, 1969).

National Nursing Assistant Survey (NNAS). The National Center for Health Statistics created the NNAS. Established in 2004 as a supplement to the 2004 National Nursing Home Survey, it offered a better understanding of the long-term care direct care workforce (Squillace et al., 2007). The NNAS was the first nationally represented survey of nursing assistants working in U.S. nursing homes.

Structural Empowerment. According to Kanter (1979), structural empowerment is how much nursing assistants can complete job tasks within their work environments by activating resources, access to information, receiving support, and having access to training that will allow them to grow professionally and individually (Laschinger et al., 2004).

Access to support. Refers to the consent to exercise innovative autonomous actions that encompass the exercise of decisions without being subjected to a complex approval procedure (Laschinger et al., 1997).

Access to opportunities. Access to opportunities refers to the facilitation of employee growth and career upward mobility through continuous training and their involvement in engaging and challenging work (Laschinger et al., 1997).

Access to information. Healthcare administrators or organizations ensure that organizational policies, procedures, goals, and values are readily available to employees

(Laschinger et al., 1999).

Access to resources. According to Laschinger et al. (1999), having access to resources is when an employee has the time necessary to complete duties, the ability to seek help when needed, equipment, and supplies required to accomplish their assigned tasks.

Turnover intention. According to Tett and Meyer (1993), turnover intention denotes the conscious attitude of an employee to leave their organization. Often described as the last step in an arrangement of withdrawal thoughts, the turnover intention is an arrangement of ideas in which the employee thinks of quitting their job, moving on to their intent to search for other job opportunities (Tett & Meyer, 1993).

Summary

This quantitative correlational study examines the relationships between structural empowerment, job satisfaction, and turnover intention in CNAs who work in nursing homes across the U.S. In Chapter 2, the literature review will draw upon present findings grounded and supported by past scholarly research and nurse empowerment expertise.

Chapter II: Literature Review

A variety of sources for peer-reviewed journal articles included MEDLINE, PubMed, EBSCO, Google Scholar, American Nurses Association, National Institute of Health, Office of the Assistant Secretary of Planning and Evaluation, Research Gate, Elsevier, SAGE, ProQuest, and the Online Journal of Issues in Nursing published between 2007 and 2021. The following search terms were used, job satisfaction, certified nursing assistants, migrant direct care workers, structural empowerment, and nursing aide.

Once a study was identified for further reviewing, the author(s) named was added as an additional keyword search term to reveal additional articles. Abstracts were studied to define the studies' relevance to include this research based on the standards identified below:

1. Omission criteria included articles published before 2007.
2. Once the article was identified, the results of the studies were prudently looked over and examined.

The Aging Population

The cohort born during the post-World War II baby boom (people born between 1946 and 1964) in the United States, called the baby boomers, has been driving change in the age structure of the U.S. population since their birth (Colby & Ortman, 2014). This cohort is projected to continue to influence the characteristics of the nation in the years to come. The baby boomers turned 65 in 2011 and are now driving growth at the older ages of the population. By 2029, when the baby boomers will be 65 years and over, over 20 percent of the total U.S.

population will be over the age of 65. Although the number of baby boomers will decline through mortality, this shift toward an increasingly older population is expected to endure. By 2056, the population 65 years and over is projected to become larger than the population under 18 years, increasing from 12.5% to 20% of the U.S. population (Center for Health Workforce Studies, 2006; Colby & Ortman, 2014). According to the Middle series projection, between 2012 and 2060, the U.S. population is projected to grow from 314 million in 2012 to 420 million in 2060, an increase of 34 percent (Acker et al., 2015). The nation will also become more racially and ethnically diverse, with the aggregate minority population projected to become the majority in 2043.

A study conducted by the New York Center for Health Workforces Studies at the SUNY School of Public Health revealed in its report these key findings:

1. Many health professions lacked diversity
2. Most health professionals receive minimal geriatric training
3. The future demand for geriatric care will be affected by
4. Health insurance reimbursement policies
5. The latest health care technologies
6. New forms and deliveries of care
7. Changes in the profession-specific scope of practice (Center for Health Workforce Studies, 2006)

The thorough report revealed the current and future trends in the health workforce and the aging of the U.S. population emphasizing areas for concern and policy consideration. Among these areas, lack of diversity in many health professions, the need for geriatric training for generalists, and specialists, and developing technologies to house and monitor the current supply, demand for, and the utilization of geriatric healthcare professionals. To meet these demands, studies are needed to observe these concerns insignificant detail to report important data so the courses of action can be taken to assure older Americans have proper access to health care.

The term “baby boomer” refers to individuals born in the United States between mid-1946 and mid-1964 (Hogan et al., 2008). Distinctions between the baby boom cohort and birth cohorts from preceding and subsequent years become apparent when fertility measures are framed within a historical context. The baby boom in the United States was marked by a substantial rise in birth rates post-World War II.

The Diverse Caring Labor Workforce

Nursing assistants make up a significant vulnerable portion of the U.S. workforce. These workers are often women and overwhelmingly represent various racial and ethnic minority backgrounds (Dill et al., 2013). Migrant workers make up a significant portion of Certified Nursing Assistants (CNAs) in the U.S. According to Sloane et al. (2010), 13.9% of CNAs are migrants. In their research, Bishop et al. (2009) findings were closely related to past studies that have brought to light the disrespect from supervisors, employers, patients, and their families by nursing assistants.

The success of efforts to recruit, retain, and maintain a long-term care workforce depends on a variety of interdependent factors. One important influence on individuals' decisions to enter and remain in the long-term care field is how society values the job. Frontline worker jobs in long-term care are viewed by the public as low wage, unpleasant occupations that involve primarily house cleaner services and care of incontinent, cognitively unaware old people. This image is exacerbated by media reports that feature poor quality care by providers. (Acker et al., 2015; Stone & Wiener, 2001).

Khatutsky et al. (2010) noted finding non-US citizens were more satisfied than U.S. citizens in their research on migrant nursing assistants. This may be due to citizens have higher expectations about working conditions. Little research has however been conducted on foreign workers in nursing homes, either alone or in comparison with native workers (Ko et al., 2015; Sloane et al., 2010). Available research provides diverging insights for international workers (Rakovski & Price-Glynn, 2010).

For many years, immigration has stabilized labor shortages in the healthcare industry. A large quantity of today's healthcare workforce consists of migrant workers. Within the U.S., a sizable migrant population exists, almost 40 million or 12.9 percent, according to the 2010 American Community Survey (Schenker, 2011). Globalization and migration have affectedly increased the multi-cultural features of the health workforce. The United States not only attracts migrants from neighboring Mexico, but migrants from African, Arab, and Asian nations are also arriving as well offering a larger diverse array of cultures and countries (Sloane et al., 2010).

Certified Nursing Assistants

Over the last few months, direct care workers faced many challenges, while continuing to support our most vulnerable community members. They were not only expected to provide residents assistance with their daily living activities, but they were also expected to work in potentially deadly work environments with the onset of the Coronavirus (COVID-19). Despite COVID-19-related safety concerns, inadequate supplies, and ongoing questions about how to access essential services like childcare (South Carolina Health Connections, 2020). A workforce projected to serve almost half of all adults 65 and older, home health aides, personal care aides, and certified nursing assistants have always been essential to the health and well-being of our communities. However, in today's public health crisis, these workers work tirelessly providing older adults with the day-to-day care they need.

Over 600,000 nursing assistants provide personal care, assistance with daily activities, and clinical support to 1.4 million nursing home residents nationwide (Paraprofessional Healthcare Institute, 2018). Direct care workers not only assist patients with their ADLs, but also provide emotional support to their patients (Almeida et al., 2020). Despite seeing a trend toward home and community-based services, nursing homes continue to play an integral role in the long-term services and support the system, providing 24-hour support to people who cannot live comfortably or safely at home (Carrington College Blog, 2014; PHI, 2020).

The poor quality of nursing assistant jobs makes it difficult for nursing homes to attract and retain enough workers to meet demand. Changing demographics could exacerbate these

staffing challenges. Nursing homes are expected to create about 59,000 new nursing assistant jobs from 2014 to 2024 (Paraprofessional Healthcare Institute, 2018). In coming years, the rapidly growing population of older adults will drive demand even higher: by 2050, the population of adults over the age of 65, who comprise 85 percent of the nursing home resident population, is projected to double, from 47.8 million to 88 million (Paraprofessional Healthcare Institute, 2018).

CNA Demographics

Nine in ten nursing assistants are women, with one in five nursing assistants being between the ages of 16 to 24 (PHI, 2020). Most are under the age of 45 with the average age being 36. With people of color comprising one-quarter of the total U.S. workforce, most of the nursing assistant workforce is Black or African American. Twenty percent of nursing assistants were born outside of the U.S., while over 90 percent are U.S. citizens. Half of the CNA workforce possesses no completed education beyond high school.

Direct care workers paid through either Medicare, Medicaid, or any other federal program with the occupation title of “home health aides” must have a minimum level of preparation similar to that of Certified Nursing Aides (CNAs), in some states called “Certified Nursing Assistants” (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2022). Like CNAs, home health aides must be able to pass a competency examination in specific areas, such as safely helping a person to eat and move from a bed to a chair and reading and reporting vital signs (Code of Federal Regulations, title 42, sec. 484.4) (Institute of Medicine, 2008).

The Omnibus Budget Reconciliation Act of 1987 created the Nurse Aide Training and Competency Evaluation Program. This act established the federal regulations that require nurse aides who work in Medicare or Medicaid-certified nursing homes or home health agencies to complete at least 75 hours of combined classroom and practical training, 16 hours of which must be supervised practical training (Henrici, 2013; Institute of Medicine, 2008). Some states have added additional requirements that extend federal training hour minimums (Institute of Medicine, 2008). The District of Columbia and twenty-seven states require over 75 hours of initial training. Twelve states, besides the District of Columbia, require 120 hours or more training hours (Institute of Medicine, 2008).

According to the United States Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS), nursing assistants occupied around 1.5 million jobs in 2012 (Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2014). However, the BLS anticipates the demand to increase to 38% by 2026 for nursing assistants (Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2022). In addition, one study in 2007 stated there were over 60,000 vacancies for Certified Nursing Assistants (CNAs) in nursing homes (Khatutusky et al., 2011). Direct care workers deliver roughly between 70-80 percent of the compensated long-term-care and personal care assistance services utilized by Americans either aging, considered elderly, or living with a disability or chronic condition that requires their assistance in accomplishing their day-to-day tasks (Paraprofessional Healthcare Institute, 2015). Between 2008 and 2018, home health aides and personal care aides are predicted to be the third and fourth highest growing career fields in the United States (Paraprofessional Healthcare Institute, 2015).

COVID-19. The past few months have brought stories of frontline, direct care workers who continue to support our most vulnerable community members despite COVID-19-related safety concerns, inadequate supplies, and ongoing questions about how to access essential services like childcare. In a workforce projected to serve almost half of all adults 65 and older, home health aides, personal care aides, and certified nursing assistants have always been essential to the health and well-being of our communities. During a public health crisis, these workers are saving lives by providing older adults with the day-to-day care they need.

Just as the COVID-19 outbreak is underscoring the significance of these workers, it is also revealing long-standing, universal shortcomings in how the U.S. supports those who deliver paid care to our elderly population. Long before the recent health crisis, the direct care workforce was inundated by low wages, poor benefits, and insufficient training. Now, amidst a public health epidemic, these preexisting susceptibilities are generating hazardous cracks in our healthcare system.

Nursing homes, that need more nursing assistants, recently have received the ability to increase their workforce in the wake of COVID-19. The Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services recently waived the rule 42 CFR §483.35(d), (except for 42 CFR §483.35(d)(1)(I)) which states, new nursing assistants are no longer required to become certified after working for four months (Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services, 2020). These requirements have been waived to assist facilities with potential staffing shortages experienced with the COVID-19 pandemic. However, this policy does not wave 483.35(d)(1)(i), which mandates facilities to not

use any person operating in the capacity of nurse aide greater than four months, on a full-time basis, unless that person is capable to deliver nursing and nursing-related services (Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services, 2020). In support of this effort to safeguard residents, the American Health Care Association/National Center for Assisted Living developed a temporary nurse-aide training and competency checklist for skilled care facilities to use when they hire temporary workers.

Foreign Nursing Assistants

Migrant workers contribute more than increasing workforces in the U.S. Due to migrants more often having varied skillsets than native-born workers; they stimulate economic growth by helping to fill gaps in the labor market. Migrant workers are overrepresented at the upper and lower ends of the skills range (Griswold, 2017). However, native-born workers are more likely to occupy the middle-skill levels (Griswold, 2017). These findings support the complementary nature of immigration as migrant workers were found to not compete directly with many native-born workers (Griswold, 2017). Occupations such as nursing assistants, and nursing aides, fall in the lower skills range. Migrant workers in lower skills occupations, occupy positions few Americans are interested in. In addition, they accept these positions at pay rates that enable their industries to remain competitive in U.S. workforce markets (Griswold, 2017). Such jobs were filled by native adult workers without high school diplomas. However, the amount of these workers in that category, continues to decline (Griswold, 2017). Between 2000 and 2016, the

number of native-born workers aged 25 and older who had not completed their high school education, declined falling from 20.5 million to 13.5 million (Griswold, 2017).

According to the LeadingAge LTSS (long-term services and supports) Center at University of Massachusetts-Boston, one-fourth of CNAs and one-third of homecare workers are migrants (The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018). In their longitudinal study, they found foreign-born nurses made up 5% of those working in long-term care facilities in Europe and North America (The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018). However, personal care assistants, make up 19-25% of LTC facility's workforces in Canada, Ireland, the United Kingdom, and the United States (The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018). They noted most providers who employ foreign-born workers experience positive outcomes as these workers take pride in their work and want to succeed in their occupations (The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018). Finally, providers must recall that many common fears around hiring foreign-born workers are unjustified. With most foreign-born workers taking pride in their work and wanting to succeed in doing so, providers must maintain and remember, their reports of their positive experiences with employing migrant-nursing assistants (The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018).

Using a three-year pooled sample from the 2011-2013 American Community Survey, (Patterson et al., 2017) conducted a descriptive study and found noncitizens employed in the healthcare labor force, are more likely to be subjected to significant social and labor market susceptibility than their naturalized citizens or native-born citizens. They acknowledged additional research is needed to comprehend the duration of their careers, the work history

patterns of various migrant groups, and how these configurations impact health career pathways and mobility. In addition, more needs to be revealed to show how the United States (U.S.) recruitment of migrants into allied health careers, influences the labor market and the population health of the U.S. (Patterson et al., 2017).

Recruitment

In the mid-1990s, the U.S. was prompted to create federal policies that allowed more migrant nurses to enter the U.S. to help fill gaps in healthcare industries due to nursing shortages (Muslin et al., 2015). Over the years, U.S. policymakers faced challenges in their ability to impact changes experienced in importing foreign-born nurses due to various reasons. These obstacles include: (a) the effects of September 11, 2001, terrorist attack on U.S. soil, (b) economic slow-downs and restricted controls on work visas, and (c) the present U.S. Presidential administration has expressed concerns with their declaration of hiring migrant nurses for U.S. healthcare systems, is not in the best interest of the U.S., recommending these jobs being filled by native-born citizens (Muslin et al., 2015).

The American Nursing Association (ANA), a primary stakeholder in the recruitment of migrant nurses, has a history of influencing hospitals and the recruitment of migrant nurses (Muslin et al., 2015). The ANA believes nurses should be able to find opportunities wherever they choose. However, in more recent years, in testimony before a U.S. Congressional subcommittee, the ANA united with the American Hospital Association (AHA) in acknowledging the international recruitment of nurses into the U.S. healthcare workforce is a

short-term method of offering a long-term solution to the labor market (Muslin et al., 2015).

Both organizations believe the long-term solution to the nursing shortage issues experienced in the U.S., will be resolved by investing in domestic nursing education (Muslin et al., 2015)

Long-term care (LTC) providers report they are finding it challenging to recruit workers with a labor market in which, job vacancies far exceed the number of workers (The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018). LTC providers receive few native-born applicants due to their lack of interest in LTC occupations. These providers maintain they could not provide LTC services without the support of migrant nurses and nursing assistants (The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018).

Migrant certified nursing assistants are more likely to be recruited using informal social networks that connect migrant CNAs in the host communities with other jobseekers currently living in their communities of origin (The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018). These networks afford care providers inexpensive access to potential candidates, as this referral system links migrant workers with long-term care career opportunities. It also minimizes the risk of hiring new staff due to recommenders are careful as to who they refer as it may affect their employment (The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018).

According to the Leading Age LTSS Center (2018), several benefits come in employing foreign-born long-term care workers. They include:

1. Positively affected quality of care-research and interviews with LTC providers reveal hiring foreign-born workers in LTC facilities, does not always directly affect the quality

of care (The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018). Conversely, providers who reported on quality care, noted positive effects.

2. Candidates who are well-suited-Both LTC administrators and residents have noted migrant N.A.s arrive with several positive traits that make them a good match for the LTC industry. They arrive with significant informal experience due to being raised in cultures that embrace the expectation of younger adults to care for their aging family members.
3. Diversity-Hiring migrant NAS helps LTC providers to create diverse working environments that foster a culturally conscious system of care that meets the demands of an increasingly diverse aging population.
4. Increases labor pools-In having the ability to tap into a human resource network of migrant nurses and nursing assistants, LTC providers can establish an alternate pool of workers that will enable them to fill labor shortages and allow LTC providers the ability to provide quality care to residents.
5. Low turnover-Research shows foreign-born workers exhibit more loyalty and are less likely to cause a turnover, than their native-born counterparts (The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018).

Structural Empowerment

Over the years, empowerment has been researched at three levels: psychological, sociological, and organizational. The concept of empowerment is closely aligned with this thrust

to gain organizational effectiveness through the wise utilization of human resources (Chen et al., 2018). Empowerment is often defined as the delegation of authority and decentralization of decision-making (Kiefer et al., 2005). From a broader perspective, empowerment is the ability for management to create and foster a workplace environment that molds an individual's perceptions of his or her job role, so it encourages positive work behavior (Conger & Kanungo, 1988).

Empowerment for nurses may consist of three components: a workplace that has the requisite structures to promote empowerment; a psychological belief in one's ability to be empowered; and acknowledgment there is power in the relationships and care provided by nurses. A more thorough understanding of these three components may help nurses to become empowered and use their power for better patient care (Manojlovich & Laschinger, 2007). According to Kanter (1993), structural empowerment means strengthening the structures in delegating independent authority, vote, responsibility, and decision-making opportunities to employees (Eskandari et al., 2017). Much has been written about empowerment at three levels: individual/psychological, sociological, and management/organizational. The focus here is on the management/organizational perspective regarding how perceived structural empowerment in N.A.s' work environments may affect their turnover intention.

Empowerment is often explained as the delegation of authority and decentralization of decision-making. However, when empowerment is more broadly defined, it speaks to the ability of management to create a working environment that shapes an individual's perceptions of his or

her work role, so it motivates positive work behavior (Conger & Kanungo, 1988). This broader definition of empowerment includes workers' perceptions of the meaning of their job to them, their sense of competence in the job, how much self-determination they believe they have in the job, and how much affect they believe they have in their job (Thomas & Velthouse, 1990). Using a cross-sectional research design to conduct secondary data analysis using the 2016-2017 Nursing Home Culture Change ($N = 1386$), Berridge et al. (2020), found greater leadership and staff empowerment levels were consistently related to N.A. retention. However, their secondary data analysis of the 2004 NNAS, found a positive relationship between supervisor support and job satisfaction and a negative relationship with turnover intention (Choi & Johantgen, 2012).

In their systematic review of individual and organizational contributing factors of job satisfaction in care aides, who worked in skilled nursing facilities, five of the studies that examined the relationship between empowerment and job satisfaction, under the category of healthcare provider characteristics, found empowerment and autonomy to have a significant positive relationship with care aide job satisfaction (Squires et al., 2015).

However, some noted that all five studies in that category had either weak or low moderate methodological qualities (Squires et al., 2015). Systematic reviews reveal challenges with the internal validity of the studies reviewed. It was recommended in future studies that were focused on factors related to care aide job satisfaction, to focus on the methodological quality of the study to minimize bias and increase confidence in knowledge on the subject.

Kanter's Structural Empowerment Theory

In her theory, Kanter (1979) states, attitudes and behaviors are formed in response to the worker's position within their organization. She goes further to indicate, a subordinate's access to empowerment structures (access to opportunity, information, support, and resources) is greatly influenced by their administrator or supervisor, which may further influence their turnover intention or desire to leave their position. In skilled nursing facility environments, nursing assistants are mainly supervised by registered nurses or licensed practical nurses. This places R.N.s and LPNs in positions to influence nursing assistants' access directly and indirectly to information, support, resources, and opportunity to accomplish goals and tasks within an organization (Kanter, 1979). Kanter indicated the three indicators of power structures were: access to resources, information, and support (Kanter, 1979). According to Kanter, individuals without access to these structures, experience a sense of powerlessness often become frustrated and may become disengaged from their organizations (Kanter, 1979). However, those who possess access to these power structures, feel in control over the work conditions that enable them to feel motivated and can share their empowerment with their peers.

Access to opportunity

The structure of opportunity refers to work conditions that offer employees a chance at upward mobility in their professions. In addition, they have options to strengthen and develop their knowledge and skills. Employees at the high end of the opportunity spectrum are proactive in their approach to problem-solving and open to change (Laschinger et al., 2010). Those who

are on the lower end of the spectrum, are less committed to their organizations and display a “stuck” type of behavior and oppose change (Laschinger et al., 2010). Stone, et al., (2017) found imminent work incentives to likely affect a worker’s evaluation of whether they should have been in their current position.

Using a random sample of 72 nursing homes across five states (Colorado, Michigan, New York, Florida, and Oregon), Castle et al., (2007) found overall high job satisfaction was related to low scores on N.A. contemplating on leaving, considering searching for a new job, and turnover. In looking at the association between the study's job satisfaction subscales and intent to leave and turnover, they revealed high work schedule subscale scores, increased training subscale scores, and high rewards subscale scores were connected to low scores on thinking about leaving, thinking about a job search, searching for a job, and turnover (Castle et al., 2007).

Access to support

Nursing assistants often work alone in work environments that encompass, low wages, long hours, stress, and burnout. Through this, they must provide a high quality of care to residents entrusted in their care. Studies have shown the importance of having and maintaining healthy and supportive work environments that encourage In line with the literature, Karantzas, et al., (2012) found supervisor support presented a significant association with job satisfaction and the intention to leave in their study. Rahnfield et al. (2016), used the Job Demands-Resources model to describe indirect and buffering effects between job demands (time pressure, social conflicts) and resources (task identity, supervisory support, and co-worker support) via

nurses' perceived health and job satisfaction on their intent to leave. Their results showed demands and resources predicted intention to leave with job satisfaction having a mediating effect. They revealed additional demands in nursing homes (Rahnfield et al., 2016). However, no differences in resources were found.

Ng and Sorensen's study (2008) showed stronger effects of supervisor support on job satisfaction and turnover intention. In addition, they were surprised to see co-worker support played no role as an antecedent of intention to leave in the study's sample. Tourangeau et al. (2010) revealed in their study of nurses working in-home care; support could occur outside of physical presence, i.e., via phone. Investigating the level of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and turnover intention, their relationships, and the buffering effect of supervisor support amongst nurses post-Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) outbreak, Jung et al. (2019) revealed PTSD was positively linked with turnover intention. In addition, they found supervisor support had a significant buffer effect on the relationship.

Access to information

A lack of adequate training and resources explains part of the ongoing struggle to recruit and retain enough direct care workers. Problematic, at the best of times, these challenges are exacerbated under certain circumstances. Workers across the country continue to complain about the lack of adequate protective equipment and guidance on care techniques.

Access to resources

The second dimension of structural empowerment, access to resources, refers to the capacity to obtain vital materials, supplies, currency, having adequate supplies and personnel required to meet organizational goals (Laschinger et al., 1999). In addition, access to resources involves employees, being allowed sufficient time necessary to complete their duties, seek help when needed, have access to the equipment and supplies necessary to complete their assigned tasks (Laschinger et al., 2010).

In their NNAS study on CNA work-related injuries, Khatutsky et al. (2012) reported over 40 percent of all CNAs said they did not have enough time for assisting patients with their ADL care and had a greater than 30 percent increased probability of being injured on the job. In addition, they found twenty-two percent of the respondents reported having to work mandatory overtime and that mandatory overtime may be linked to staffing shortages. With overtime comes exhaustion and that could place the N.A. and or patient at risk for injuries and errors. Using multivariate analyses in their study, they examined job satisfaction from the aspects of workplace environment characteristics that included: nursing assistant wages, the time allowed for tasks, workplace morale, performing challenging work, and learning new skills.

Problematic at the best of times, these challenges are exacerbated under circumstances. Workers across the country continue to voice concerns about the lack of adequate protective equipment and guidance on care techniques. The recently passed Coronavirus Aid, Relief, and Economic Security (CARES) Act provides for additional training and supplies for health care

workers, including those in the direct care workforce (The Bell Policy Center, 2020). However, as the epidemic spreads, this support must be maintained.

Turnover Intention

One significant challenge Americans are facing in the 21st Century is the possibility of not having enough certified nursing assistants available to guarantee, individuals who require their activities of daily living (ADLs) and support, will have a supply that meets their demands. In 2003, the Bureau of Labor Statistics projected that by 2010, the direct care work industry would see a 45 percent increase or 800,000 jobs (Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2000). However, by 2030, the demand will continue at a steady pace as direct care workers, who worked in skilled nursing facilities, will see an increase in demand as the baby boomer generation reaches the age of 85 that year (DHHS, et. al., 2003). For nursing administrators, one of their most significant issues, is the recruitment and retention of nursing assistants, personal care aides, and home health aides, the front-line care providers of healthcare (DHHS, et. al., 2003). These workers are vital because they provide essential hands-on assistance in aiding their clients with their ADLs.

Turnover intention is among one of the most important activities in which the human resources management of an organization is always a concern (Kaur et al., 2013). The reason for such consideration given to job turnover is due to organizations investing a lot of resources in employees from their training and development, compensation plans, and perspective building to achieve the organizations' goals, missions, and objectives (Coogole et al., 2007; Kazi & Zadeh, 2011;). While job satisfaction and employment intentions influence nursing assistant turnover,

Dill et al., (2013) hypothesized in their study, that the relationship between job satisfaction, intent to stay, and retention is less significant for N.A.s compared to workers in a higher wage status. They stated the effect of lack of resources on N.A.s' employment status, may be independent of a N.A.'s job satisfaction and their intention to stay, as people often cannot foresee when economic, personal, or family challenges will occur (Dill et al., 2013). According to the literature, (Barbera, 2014; Barry et al., 2008; Murkamel et al., 2009), the turnover rate for direct care workers is noteworthy and has reached rates over 100% within some organizations. In addition, high turnover is related to low job satisfaction (Castle et al., 2007).

Considerable research has been done to study the factors that influence DSW turnover and turnover intention. Much of this research has been conducted either in the aging and physical disabilities sector or in the intellectual and developmental disabilities sector and the least has been completed in the behavioral health sector (Applebaum et al., 2010; Kaur et al., 2013; Schyns et al., 2007). On a random sample of CNAs from the Pennsylvania Department of Health's CNA registry, a longitudinal study to study job factors and work attitudes linked with full-time staying or leaving, Rosen et al. (2011), found nursing assistants who switched jobs reported increased turnover intentions and lower benefits compared to CNAs who stayed and those who left for new opportunities. In addition, their study revealed CNAs who left had lower job satisfaction and emotional well-being and left their job for health reasons, revealing turnover intentions to predict low job satisfaction and low emotional well-being.

Using a multiple linear regression in a cross-sectional survey of 1978 nurses, who worked in 48 hospitals across Jiangsu Province, Chen et al. (2018), corroborated high turnover intention in nurses. In their study, they found variables: involvement in hospital affairs, resource adequacy, age, professional title, working years, mode of employment, and education level predicted turnover intention. They revealed in their univariate analysis, the variable, the department was considered a key factor for the work environment, burnout, and turnover intention (Chen et al., 2018). These findings followed the findings of (Wan et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2018). However, examining the predictors of turnover intention in their multistage cluster sampling method, Wang, et al., (2020) found work environment satisfaction, medical practicing environment satisfaction, and organizational management satisfaction proved negative predictors of turnover intention ($p < 0.05$).

Turnover Intention and Supervisory Support

Another contributing factor to high Certified Nursing Assistant turnover rates, relates to the employee's working relationship with their supervisors. In the nursing home setting, Certified Nursing Assistants are directly supervised by Registered Nurses and Licensed Practical Nurses. Choi and Johantgen (2012) explain that Certified Nursing Assistants can feel a lack of appreciation and respect from their supervisors. This perceived lack of gratitude or appreciation is cited as one of the most common reasons for Certified Nursing Assistant turnover in skilled nursing facilities. A study by Choi and Johantgen (2012) states "For each one-unit increase in supportive supervision, CNAs were 4.09 times more likely to be satisfied with their jobs and

47% less likely to intend to leave their jobs.” The study defined supportive supervision through ten items including: “treats all CNAs equally, deals with CNAs’ complaints and concerns, is open to new ideas, helps the CNAs with job tasks, supports CNAs working in teams, tells CNAs when they are doing a good job, provides clear instructions, disciplines CNAs not performing well, listens to the CNAs’ concerns about residents’ care, and is supportive of progress in the CNA’s career” (Choi & Johantgen, 2012). Choi and Johantgen (2012) explain, “The score of the 10 items was totaled to obtain the mean score. The possible score range was from 1 to 4; a higher score indicated a more supportive supervisor.” The perception of being valued by their employer or supervisor is significant in Certified Nursing Assistant retention, as it is also a leading factor in their job satisfaction. Supportive supervision can also affect Certified Nursing Assistants' intent to leave their positions in long-term care (Choi, et. al). Individuals who feel they are more supported and appreciated by their direct supervisor or administrator are less likely to express intent to self-terminate their positions.

Turnover Intention and Personal Characteristics

The need to obtain a greater understanding of factors contributing to vacancy rates and increased turnover is essential in improving the retention of nursing assistants. Demographics are more often considered control variables in opposed to significant predictors of job satisfaction and turnover in some turnover models (Price, 2001). Chen et al. (2018) study indicated results in line with several turnover intention studies. They found nurse’s age, professional title, type of employment, number of working years, and their education level were significantly related to

turnover intention (Bishop et al., 2009; Chen et al., 2018). Their study indicated nurses, age 29 and younger and was the largest age group of the study, had a significantly higher turnover intention (Chen et al., 2018). In studying work-family conflict and turnover intention, Alshutwi (2017) supports this in finding several demographic variables including, age, gender, marital status, and parental demand. However, in a study population of R.N.s employed in five hospitals in Calgary, Canada, age, and education were shown to have a negative effect on turnover intention (Osujim et al., 2014).

Squillace et al. (2007) reported in their study, NAs who were younger, widowed, divorced, or separated, had higher education, were non-U.S. citizens, spoke languages other than English as their primary language, and had lower tenure in their present position and during their career, were most likely to intend to leave. In their analyses, Sloane et al. (2010) revealed migrants varied significantly from their U.S. born citizen nursing assistant counterparts. Certified nursing assistants who were noncitizens, were more likely to report plans to leave their jobs. They noted the estimated risk for leaving their job within 1 year was nearly twice as significant as U.S.-born citizens, being independent of satisfaction and client relationship, proposes citizenship status should be added to the list of risk factors for turnover (Sloane et al., 2010).

Conducting secondary data analysis on the same source as this study (NNAS), the researchers were revealed a few of the N.A.s' personal characteristics were significantly correlated to the study's measures of intent to leave (Stearns & D'Arcy, 2008). For instance, younger participants were found to more likely to be actively seeking other career opportunities.

Besides indicating an intent to leave their present job, Hispanics were the opposite, as they were less likely to be seeking other career opportunities and non-whites were more likely to intend to leave the occupations altogether (Stearns & D'Arcy, 2008). Stearns and D'Arcy (2008) analyzed the N.A.s' educational levels and found that higher levels of education to be positively connected with significant intent to leave their skilled-nursing facility and their CNA careers (Stearns & D'Arcy, 2008).

Turnover research has traditionally examined intention to turnover rather than actual turnover. Such studies assume that leave intent serves equally well as both a proxy for and predictor of employees' actual turnover behavior. Cohen et al. (2016) used a hierarchical (stepwise) multiple regression analysis to determine the usefulness of studying turnover intent as a dependable proxy and predictor of actual turnover using a population that extended over 180 U.S. federal agencies. Their findings suggested, turnover intention and actual turnover are separate concepts predicted by dissimilar groups of variables (Cohen et al, 2016). Based upon these findings, they concluded public managers whose duties consisted of employee retention, would receive better foresight if they focused on their agencies distinguished demographic characteristics and detailed business practices, in opposed to centering in on the employee's combined perceived turnover intention rate (Cohen et al., 2016).

Job Satisfaction

The concept of job satisfaction is defined in various ways across the literature. Despite its variation, job satisfaction most utilized definition in organizational research, is that of Locke

(1976) definition which describes job satisfaction as “a pleasurable or positive state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job or job experiences (p. 1304). Ensher et al. (2001) define job satisfaction as a pleasing or positive emotional state that occurs from the assessment of one’s occupation or work experiences. Castle et al. (2007) goes on to define job satisfaction, “favorableness or unfavorableness in which employees identify their work.” Cicolini et al. (2013), defined job satisfaction as a positive concept that describes work behaviors in work environments.

Explore the job satisfaction of nursing assistants as it affects the quality of care and resident life nursing home and home health care agencies offer. In qualitative studies conducted, researchers feel the belief in the essential importance of caring labor (Berdes & Eckert, 2007; Castle et al., 2007). Whenever workers have direct contact with their patients or clients, their satisfactions were influenced by the workers’ attitude (Bishop et al., 2009). In a study conducted by the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services (HHS), while participants were less satisfied with their benefits and salaries, roughly 60% of direct care workers reported being satisfied or somewhat satisfied with their jobs.

Job satisfaction as a work environment construct has been a great interest in various research studies (Abrahamson et al., 2011; Gaugler, 2014;). Exploring the job satisfaction of nursing assistants is important due to its impact on patients’ quality care. In qualitative studies previously researchers feel the belief in the essential importance of caring labor (Berdes & Eckert, 2007; Castle et al, 2007). In their study regarding work environment, (Gunnarsdittir et

al., 2009), job satisfaction, burnout, nurse-assessed quality of care, they found work environment a positive indicator of job satisfaction and nurses' perception of quality of care. Breaus & Rheame (2014), concluded both empowerment and work environment were strong predictors of job satisfaction and that workplace environment contributed to the formation of positive work environments and raised job satisfaction among nurses who worked in Intensive Care Units (ICU). Whenever workers have direct contact with their patients or clients, their satisfactions are influenced by the workers' attitude (Bishop et al., 2009). In a study conducted by the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services (HHS), while participants were less satisfied with their benefits and salaries, roughly 60% of direct care workers reported being satisfied or somewhat satisfied with their jobs (Khatutsky et al., 2012). Note, not every dissatisfied employee will leave their job. This dissatisfaction may be revealed negatively in their daily tasks, how they interact with their peers, and impact the quality of care provided to their patients (Squires et al., 2015).

Job dissatisfaction is linked with psychological issues including emotional exhaustion, burnout, despair, anxiety, and frustration besides physical conditions (de Castro et al., 2008). When people are dissatisfied with their jobs, it not only influences their health and well-being, but it also affects their productivity at work. Productivity is important especially in health care when patients such as those found in nursing facilities and those who require home health assistance, require, and expect to receive quality care. Using a sample of 72 nursing homes from five states (Colorado, Florida, Michigan, New York, and Oregon, researchers conducted

qualitative research to study the relationship between job satisfaction of nursing assistants and the intent to leave and genuine turnover over a one-year period (Castle et al., 2007). Scientists utilized a job satisfaction instrument and logistic regression for the data analysis that resulted their study revealing a high overall job satisfaction was linked to low scores on the intent to leave, thinking about new career opportunities, searching for a new job, and turnover. They used the Nursing Home Nurse Aide Job Satisfaction Questionnaire as the measurement instrument to evaluate job satisfaction of nursing assistants (Castle et al., 2007). In the study, some noted that low satisfaction was link with both intents to leave and turnover supporting both research hypotheses.

Job Satisfaction and Demographic Factors

In their systematic review of contributing factors of job satisfaction among care aides, (Squires et al., 2015) satisfaction, empowerment and autonomy were significant. However, age, ethnicity, gender, education level, attending specialized training, and their years of experience, were found not be important. However, Ko et al. (2015), found increased rating of supervisory and co-worker support predicted higher levels of job satisfaction among immigrant workers when controlling for age, income satisfaction, and job characteristics. Factors determined significant in relating to job satisfaction, offers promise as targets of nursing assistant's job satisfaction intervention (Squires et al., 2015). In the course in their systematic review about contributing factors of job satisfaction in nursing homes, Squires et al. (2015), recommended

future research to consider using research methodologies with a more vigorous research design and multivariate analysis methodologies.

Results in the literature, regarding antecedents of nurses' job satisfaction have been inconsistent in the associations with workload, age, type of nursing unit, and education (Taunton et al., 2004). In their systematic review of contributing factors of job satisfaction among care aides, (Squires et al., 2015) satisfaction, empowerment and autonomy were significant. However, age, ethnicity, gender, education level, attending specialized training, and their years of experience, were found not be important. This contradicts Lerner and colleagues (2011) findings. In their study, they used a multiple regression analysis to explore nine factors that may have influenced the job satisfaction of nursing assistants employed in Maryland skilled nursing facilities. Performance of restorative care and years of experiences were the only two factors found to be related to job satisfaction (Lerner et al., 2011).

Citizenship Status

Citizenship status may affect job satisfaction for several reasons. For example, diverse cultural backgrounds often correlate with different values and thus different expectations about work. In addition, migrants may have a lack of resources such as English communication skills and social network compared to their native counterparts (Massey & Roter, 2015; Pennington et al., 2003).

In their research, (Sloane et al., 2010) noted citizenship status was closely linked to respect (Sloane et al., 2010). However, using an adjusted bivariate analysis between resident

characteristics and the client relations, and job satisfaction items regarding citizenship status, they couldn't find a consistent trend between job satisfaction and citizenship status. Migrant workers experience "double jeopardy" of dealing with stressors related to a new working environment and living in a new country (de Castro et al., 2008; Ko et al., 2015). However, using Bart Landry's intersectional model (2006), Rakovski and Price-Glynn (2010) found race and citizenship had a significance stronger than gender in worker satisfaction. Therefore, it cannot be assumed that the determinants of job satisfaction identified for the general U.S. working population can be generalized to migrants without further investigation.

Using data from the 2002 and 2008, the authors examined how citizenship status affects determinants of job satisfaction (Ko et al., 2015). Hierarchical linear regression was used to uncover whether income satisfaction, autonomy, learning opportunities, supervisor, and coworker support predict U.S.-born and migrant workers' job satisfaction and how citizenship status moderates the relationship between each predictor and job satisfaction. Results showed the moderating effects of citizenship status for income satisfaction and autonomy on the job. The relationship between income satisfaction and job satisfaction was stronger for migrants and the relationship between autonomy on the job and job satisfaction was negative for migrants who lack English proficiency. These results add to the limited knowledge about the ever-growing migrant workforce within the United States (Ko et al., 2015).

Knowing the factors that predict job satisfaction is important for both employees and professionals who work with employees, such as frontline managers, human resource managers,

and Employee Assistance Program (EAP) professionals. It has been generally agreed upon that employees' job satisfaction is positively related to the organizational commitment level and that satisfaction reduces turnover and increases productivity (Back et al., 2011; Judge et al., 2001; Lui et al., 2019). However, there was no consistent trend among the satisfaction items regarding citizenship status (Sloane et al., 2010). Therefore, understanding the factors affecting employee job satisfaction can save employers human resource management costs and will contribute to increasing productivity. On the employees' side, job satisfaction can be a source of self-esteem and overall positive mental health and well-being (Arnett et al., 2002; & Ko et al., 2015).

In their study, Ko et al. (2015), studied how citizenship status affected determinants of job satisfaction using data from the 2002 and 2008 National Study of the Changing Workforce. Using hierarchical linear regression, they showed the moderating effects of citizenship status for income satisfaction and autonomy on the job. In addition, they found the relationship between income satisfaction and job satisfaction to be stronger among migrants who lacked a proficiency in English.

Citizenship status may affect job status for various reasons. For one, having diverse cultures in the workplace, often correlate with various values and offers different organizational expectations. For immigrant workers, life as an immigrant brings stressors that could lead to negative outcomes (Ko et al., 2015). In their exploratory analysis, Squillace et al (2008), found nursing assistants who reported they were planning to leave their organizations were mostly to be young, widowed, divorced, or separated, possessed higher education, were a non-U.S. citizen,

spoke other languages besides English as their primary language, and had a lower tenure both in their current position and the duration of their nursing assistant careers (Squillace et al., 2008).

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Kanter's (1993) theory of structural empowerment will be the theoretical framework for the study. Kanter's theory of structural empowerment has been used frequently in nursing studies (Cai & Zhou, 2009; Choi et al., 2016; Chunfeng & Zhou, 2009; Kuokkanen et al., 2003; Laschinger et al., 1997; Valdez et al., 2019). Kanter's theory of structural empowerment was selected to be the framework to guide this study based upon an extensive review of the literature in its use in nurse empowerment studies and because it explains the concepts and terms related to empowerment (Ahmad & Oranye, 2010; Aloisio et al., 2018; Barry et al., 2008; Berridge et al., 2018; Cai et al., 2011; Choi et al., 2014; Lautizi et al., 2009; Squires et al., 2015). The simple component of empowerment is the opportunity to act that will produce positive outcomes both at the individual and organizational level (Chunfeng & Zhou, 2009).

Kanter's structural empowerment theory offers a useful theoretical framework for understanding how empowering work environments can lead to positive organizational outcomes (Larkin, 2008). In her theory, Kanter asserts empowerment is elevated in work environments that offer employees access to information, resources, support, and the opportunity to develop and grow through training opportunities (Spence Laschinger et al., 2006). She goes further to state the structure of work environments are key correlate of employee attitude and behaviors in

organizations and the perceived access to these key components relate to these attitudes and behaviors (Nedd, 2006).

According to Kanter (1993), employees who feel empowered are more likely to be motivated at work in opposed to those who do not have access to these empowering structures. Laschinger et al., (1997) and Lautizi et al. (2009) contends structural empowerment was the center of work environments and incorporated organizational strategies for individuals to perform in an empowered environment and aided workers in accomplishing their work effectively.

In her structural empowerment theory, lines of power arise from formal and informal systems within organizations Orgambidez-Ramos and Borrego-Ales (2014). Kanter (1993) defined power as the “ability to mobilize resources to get things done” (p. 210). Kanter calls opportunity growth, mobility, and the chance for workers to raise their knowledge and skills. Orgambidez-Ramos and Borrego-Ales (2014) suggests in their study, that opportunity was a key predictor of job satisfaction. They found the access of opportunity to learn and develop in the workplace implied the use of personal skills and abilities, that created a sense of self-efficacy and autonomy (Orgambidez-Ramos & Borrego-Ales, 2014).

Kanter argued that organizational structures influenced workers ability to accomplish their duties (Kanter, 1993). The ability to perform one’s duties effectively influences jobs satisfaction, work effectiveness, and the levels of burnout (Laschinger et al., 2003). Nurse empowerment studies using Kanter’s theoretical model indicated positive relationships between

empowerment and hospital nurses and job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and self-efficacy (Cho et al., 2006; Laschinger et al., 2000; Laschinger et al., 2003). Over the years, research conducted by Laschinger and her contemporaries (1994, 1996, 1999, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004, 2007, & 2009), demonstrated the value in using Kanter's theory in nursing research. While her theory has corroborated the positive effects of empowering work environments, there are limitations with her theory.

Kanter's theory does not incorporate all variables linked with empowerment and centers on individuals in opposed to groups (Friend & Sieloff, 2018). In the literature base there is consistent support for Kanter's theory used within the nursing population (Ahmad & Oranye, 2010; Aloisio, et al., 2018; Barry et al., 2005; Berridge et al., 2018; Cai et al., 2009; Choi et al., 2014; Chunfeng & Zhou, 2009; Lautizi et al., 2009; Squires et al., 2015). These studies have positively associated structural empowerment to factors classified as viable for the investigation of ways to recruit and retain nurses, which includes job satisfaction (Chunfeng & Zhou, 2009), work autonomy (Squires et al., 2015), and organizational commitment (Lautizi et al., 2009). Ravitch and Riggan defines the conceptual framework as an argument in explaining why the study matters, validates why the theoretical and methodological tools used to perform the study are rigorous and appropriate (Ravitch & Riggan, 2017). The conceptual model proposed in *Figure 1*, focuses on the study's research questions and hypotheses regarding the relationship between structural empowerment (four sub-scales of access to opportunity, resources, information, and support), age, citizenship status, and turnover intentions. Ravitch and Riggan

(2017) argues; (a) the conceptual framework creates the importance of and the intended audience for the study, (b) the conceptual framework organizes and validates alignment between the topic, research questions, data collection, and the data analysis, and last, (c) the conceptual framework indicates and describes the formulation of the study's research questions, study's design selection, data collection, data analysis, and provides a way for integrating new data, findings, and questions as the study evolves.

Figure 1.

Study's proposed conceptual framework

In her theory of structural empowerment, Kanter (1979, 1993) defines power as the ability to mobilize information, resources, and support to do things in the organization. Structural empowerment is defined as the extent to which employees feel they have access to these

structures in their work settings. Kanter argues that formal power and informal power ensure access to two organizational structures that create an empowering workplace: (1) the structure of opportunity; and (2) the structure of power. The structure of opportunity provides individuals with the chance to advance within the organization and to develop their knowledge and skills. Employees in high opportunity jobs are more proactive and innovative at solving challenges in their work, while those lacking opportunity are less motivated to succeed and less productive. Power is a dynamic structure created through formal and informal systems within the organization. Formal power results from jobs that are visible, support discretion, and are central to organizational goal accomplishment. Informal power refers to the personal networks and alliances within the organization, such as relationships with sponsors, peers, and other coworkers. The structure of power in the workplace comes from three main sources: (1) access to information; (2) access to support and (3) access to the resources required for realizing organizational goals.

Hypotheses

While the research questions guide the study's design, the hypothesis navigates the statistical analysis, as the way the hypothesis is written, determines how the data will be analyzed (Houser, 2016). Based on the proposed study's theoretical framework, quantitative research design and research questions presented, the hypotheses for this study are as follows:

H₀₁: Access to opportunity do not significantly predict turnover intention.

H_{a1}: Access to opportunity significantly predict turnover intention.

H₀₂: Access to support do not significantly predict turnover intention.

H_{a2}: Access to support significantly predict turnover intention.

H₀₃: Access to information do not significantly predict turnover intention.

H_{a3}: Access to information significantly predict turnover intention.

H₀₄: Access to resources do not significantly predict turnover intention.

H_{a4}: Access to resources significantly predict turnover intention.

H₀₅: Structural empowerment do not statistically predict turnover intention.

H_{a5}: Structural empowerment significantly predict turnover intention.

H₀₆: Job satisfaction do not statistically predict turnover intention.

H_{a6}: Job satisfaction significantly predict turnover intention.

Summary

Recruiting and retaining CNAs in the United States, who work in long-term care facilities, has been the focus of several studies over the years (Berridge et al., 2018; Castle et al., 2007; Donoghue, 2009; Rosen et al., 2011). Across the U.S., a high rate of turnover among nursing assistants in long-term care facilities continues to be a significant workforce issue. Excessive turnover rates and low nursing assistant retention not only harmfully influences patient's quality of care, but it also has a significant financial impact on long-term care facilities. It is not only imperative for policymakers and administrators to strategically find successful methods of recruiting, but new strategies also that will enable this essential healthcare position to appeal and attract potential candidates to mitigate growing demands.

The researcher will follow up in Chapter 3 with the study's methodological outline which details the research design and method, identifying its appropriateness in this study, a thorough description of the sample population, disclosure of the secondary data source and confirm the confidentiality of its participants, the survey instrument's reliability and validity, and details of data analyses of the study's variables.

Chapter III: Methods

This correlational quantitative study examines the relationships between structural empowerment, job satisfaction, and turnover intention in CNAs, who work in nursing homes across the U.S. In Chapter 2, the researcher summarized scholarly articles from the knowledge base regarding structural empowerment, job satisfaction, turnover intention, and citizenship status among nurses and nursing assistants. In this chapter, the researcher will discuss the research design, methodology, and the study's population. The chapter details the data analysis plan and provides the study's ethical procedures and considerations.

Research Design and Rationale

Based upon the study's research questions and hypotheses, this observational investigation applied a descriptive correlational study method to a quantitative research design to analyze cross-sectional retrospective data from the 2004 National Nursing Assistant Survey. This study aimed to examine the associations between the four structural empowerment dimensions, overall structural empowerment, job satisfaction, citizenship status, and their predictive influence on CNA turnover intention. Based on the aims of the research, a correlational research method (a non-experimental research method) was employed instead of an experimental one. After conducting secondary data analysis, I used a quantitative research design approach to answer the research questions and test the study's hypotheses.

Quantitative research designs primarily use deductive reasoning in which the researcher starts the research with an established theory or framework, in which the concepts are condensed

into variables, and accumulating evidence to evaluate or test if the theory or framework was supported (Sousa et al., 2007). The chosen design was appropriate as it enabled the researcher to observe the indicators, at a point within a sample of CNAs and describe the relationship among the variables observed (Breakwell et al., 1995). A predictive correlation design was chosen as a regression equation to examine the structural empowerment's ability, its four dimensions, and job satisfaction to predict turnover intention while controlling for the demographic variables identified (Simon & Goes, 2018). Analyzing secondary data from the 2004 NNAS, this research used a quantitative method and a predicative correlational research design. Babbie (2010) explains that if a study aims to explain a phenomenon through numerical evidence, then the most suitable research method to use would be quantitative. A correlational research study design was chosen because it is the best method to conduct studies that demonstrate associations or relationships between one or more variables (Sousa et al., 2007). In addition, correlational research tried to identify variables with a significant relationship to the extent to which a change in one creates some change in the other. This research design aligns with the study's purpose because the design analyzes the direction, degree, or strength of the relationships or associations amongst variables. The objective of a predictive correlational research design is to predict the variance of one or more variables based on the variance of another variable (Sousa et al., 2007).

In addition, this study did not use an experimental research design. An experimental design incorporates subjects measured before and after treatment, consists of a small sample population, and is intended to establish causality between variables. For example, Kazdin (2003)

distinguishes between experimental and correlational studies. He implies that manipulation is distinctive between these two types of quantitative studies. In an experimental research study design, the researcher manipulates a variable or interest, while, in a correlational, the researcher observes the variables of interest and their associations. In this study, none of the variables were manipulated. While this study explored the problem of turnover intention within the CNA population, the limitation of the chosen correlation research design, was the conclusion about a cause-and-effect relationship among the variables could not be correlation does not indicate causation (Babbie, 2010).

Methodology

Population

The NNAS Survey is a cross-sectional survey conducted by the National Center for Health Statistics (NCHS) for the 2004 National Nursing Assistant Survey, to describe the work experiences of nursing assistants and to provide a framework for future policy and research to practice implementations and initiatives (Squillace et al., 2007). The study population consisted of 3,017 direct care workers between the ages of 16 and 65 identified as care aides, nurse aides, and certified nursing assistants. They were defined as non-professional staff members who provided direct patient care under the guidance/supervision of a registered nurse (RN), licensed practical nurse (LPN), or registered practical nurse (RPN). These healthcare providers completed a short healthcare training program in which they were equipped to aid patients and offer support services to RNs/LPNs and RPNs.

Sampling and Sampling Procedures

To ensure the study's results can reach an anticipated minimum correlation coefficient value with sufficient power and desired type I error or p-value, a sufficient sample size is required (Bujang & Baharum, 2016). This quantitative study used a total population sampling ($n = 3,017$). Total population sampling is a form of purposive sampling technique and involves examining an entire population with a particular group of characteristics (Lund Research & Inc, 2012).

The primary statistical test used in this study was binary logistic regression. One of the limitations of this statistical analysis is the sample size. For logistic regression, large sample sizes are mandatory to have adequate numbers in the binary categories of the response variable (Bewick et al., 2005). Power analysis for a regular logistic regression conducted using the guidelines established in Lipsey & Wilson (2001) indicates that the minimum sample size to yield a statistical power of at least .80, with an alpha of .05, and medium effect size (odds ratio = 1.72) is 177. Of the 3,017 cases, there were $n = 293$ observations that contained missing information when the subscale scores had to be calculated for purposes of the data analysis. An additional $n = 120$ cases were removed when the third category of the criterion variable, turnover intention, was collapsed into a dichotomous variable. The final analyses were conducted using a sample of $n = 2,604$ subjects. By these standards, conducting this study using a sample of $n = 2,604$ subjects is more than sufficient.

Materials, Instruments, and Source of Data

Secondary data was analyzed in this study. The non-identifiable dataset was available for public access on NCHS's website. The zip file was provided with complimentary public released documents (original study used for data collection, methodology, data codebook, SAS, SPSS, and STATA files (National Center for Health Statistics, 2015). The zip file was downloaded, and the csv (comma-separated value file) was extracted and saved to external hard drive. Due to the file size, limited personal characteristics and only the study's variables were copied to an excel spreadsheet and saved to the external hard drive. The file was then exported into SPSS 28 for the initial data cleaning process (see Chapter 4). The sample size was 2,604 and a post hoc power analysis was conducted to determine if there were statistically valid results.

The sampling frame for the 2004 NHHS came from two sources: The Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) Provider of Services (POS) nursing home data and the state licensing lists gathered by a private organization. Together, both files contained 17,000 nursing homes. After the combined files were matched and unduplicated, the final sampling frame of 16,628 nursing homes remained (Squillace et al., 2007). Of the sampling frame, 1,500 nursing facilities were selected. This section identified a sub-sample of facilities ($n=790$) to participate in the NNAS (Squillace et al., 2007).

From these facilities, a sample of nursing assistants, stratified by tenure were then, asked to complete the survey. A sample of 4,542 nursing assistants were identified to complete the NNAS and 4,274 were eligible to complete it based on criteria such as speaking English or

Spanish or being certified (Squillace et al., 2007). Of those eligible, 3,017 participated in the survey. The survey was completed by these participants in the nursing home facilities where the participants worked on a computer.

CNAs had to be fluent in English or Spanish to complete the survey. These participants included U.S. and non-U.S. care aides, nurse aides, and/or nursing assistants. An NA is termed a certified nurse aide (CNA) when certified by a state agency (USA). CNAs who participated in the survey were employees of U.S. nursing home (full-time or part-time) and were state certified.

Procedures for Recruitment, Participation, and Data Collection (Primary Data)

Prior to contacting participants, the NNAS survey procedures were reviewed and permitted by the National Center for Health Statistics (NCHS) Institution Review Board. After conducting on-site interviews for the 2004 National Nursing Home Survey (NNHS), nursing facilities provided a list of eligible CNAs to use for the 2004 NNAS. After screening the list, CNAs who did not meet the eligibility criteria, were removed. Participants were selected from within each sampled facility, using a systematic random sampling algorithm software. A computer-assisted personal interviewing program was used to contact participants and conduct the interview.

To proceed, the participant had to complete the postcard and return in a postage paid envelope or called the toll-free number provided in the packet and scheduled time to complete the survey (National Center for Health Statistics, 2015). CNAs who returned their postage-paid postcards or called the toll-free number received a package that contained information on the

survey and a \$5 prepaid token of appreciation for taking time to learn about the survey (National Center for Health Statistics, 2015).

Between September 2004 and February 2005, 3,017 interviews were completed in English or Spanish during non-working hours. The interview took 30 to 40 minutes to complete (National Center for Health Statistics, 2015). Once the participant completed the survey, they received an additional \$30 (Squillace et al., 2009). The NNAS overall response rate was 53.4 percent.

Participants' Inclusion Criteria

The target population for the NNAS are nursing assistants employed in nursing homes and aid residents with activities of daily living (ADL) that consist of eating, help with using the toilet, dressing, and bathing. To be employed in Medicaid/Medicare certified nursing homes, nursing assistants must be certified by the state in which they are employed. The nursing assistant can be employed full time or part-time working at least 16 hours per week. The NNAS was translated into Spanish for nursing assistants who did not speak English as a primary language.

Participants' Exclusion Criteria

The NNAS explicitly omits nursing assistants who are not certified (except for those who are in the certification process or worked as a nurse aide before the 1987 certification requirement), are working through a contractual arrangement, and can only help with instrumental ADLs like, transportation, shopping, housework, meal preparation, or the

administering of medication (Squillace et al., 2007). Nursing assistants who did not speak English or Spanish were omitted due the cost associated with providing interpretive services for additional languages.

NNAS Pilot test. Between March and April 2004, the NNAS pilot test was conducted to gauge the effectiveness of advance materials, participant's contact methods, sampling procedures, instrument implementation time and questionnaire translation, the data collection, and the quality and processing of contact information to ensure the confidentiality of the study's participants (Squillace et al., 2006).

A sample consisting of 63 nursing assistants from eight nursing facilities were used in the pilot. Out of eight nursing home administrators, only one of them provided contact information for the sampled NAs (Squillace et al., 2006). Due to this low response rate, the instrument developers created a standalone recruitment packet based upon information gathered from two focus groups and two cognitive interview sessions held in June 2004. The final advance materials for the survey were created from the feedback received from these sessions (Squillace et al., 2006).

Instrumentation Reliability

English and Spanish pretest interviews with the nurse aides were conducted with limited problems (DesRoches et al., 2004). The participants understood the purpose of the questions and there were few nonresponse items due to question sensitivity. The interviewers showed little trouble administering the questionnaire due to how the question was formatted. There were few

missed, skips, and/or interviewer errors (DesRoches et al., 2004).

Because the data on the NNAS' website are based on a sample, they will differ slightly from data obtained had a complete census been taken, and the same instructions and procedures used (Squillace et al., 2006). The standard error (SE) is largely a measure of the variability that happens by chance because only a sample is surveyed (Squillace et al., 2006). The standard error also mirrors part of the measurement error but measures no systematic biases in the data or other non-sampling error. There was a chance between 95 in 100 that an estimate from the sample varies from the value attained from a complete survey by less than twice the standard error (Squillace et al., 2007).

The standard errors in all tables presented here were approximated with SUDAAN software. SUDAAN computes standard errors by using a first-order Taylor estimate of the deviation of estimates from their projected values (Squillace et al., 2006). While some estimates are presented, they cannot be presumed reliable and are marked with an asterisk. Estimates are identified if they are based on between 30 and 59 cases; or if they are based on greater than 59 cases then have a relative standard error exceeding 30 percent (Squillace et al., 2007).

Structural Empowerment Instrument Reliability

The structural empowerment variable was measured using a summated Likert type instrument, that consisted of 14 items from the work environment, job satisfaction and organizational commitment, and manager/supervisor sections of the NNAS. The structural

empowerment scale consisted of four empowerment subscales, opportunity, support, resources, and information. A summation of the four scales were used to create structural empowerment.

Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to calculate the internal consistency coefficients of the items used to construct the structural empowerment subscales. Structural empowerment scores were normally distributed with a skewness of

-0.84 ($SE_M = 0.04$) and kurtosis = 0.36. The results of the reliability analysis revealed the items in the five scales had a satisfactory discriminating power according to Hair et al. (2010). They state while a Cronbach's alpha coefficient value of 0.70 has been collectively agreed upon as being an acceptable range, George and Mallery (2003), Pallant (2013), and Ursachi, Horodnic, & Zait (2015), states a range of 0.60 or above is acceptable. The items for opportunities had a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .62, indicating acceptable reliability. The six items used for support had a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.86, indicating good reliability, consistent with prior reported instrument reliabilities (Berridge et al., 2018; Chunfeng & Zhou, 2009; Giancardolo & Comparcini, 2013). The items for information had a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.62, indicating acceptable reliability. The items used to create resources had a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.60, indicating acceptable reliability. A summary of the subscales' reliability scores is provided in Table 1. See Appendix B for a complete detailed Cronbach's alpha summary of the 14-item instrument used to measure structural empowerment and the subscales.

Table 1.*Reliability Table for Sub-Scales of Structural Empowerment*

Scale	No. of Items	α	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
OPPORTUNITY	4	0.62	0.60	0.64
SUPPORT	6	0.86	0.86	0.87
INFO	2	0.62	0.60	0.65
RESOURCES	2	0.60	0.57	0.63

Note. The lower and upper bounds of Cronbach's α were calculated using a 95% confidence interval.

Instrument Content Validity

A review of the instrumentation used in the 2004 NNAS survey, (Squillace et al., 2007), which encompassed the methods used to improve reliability and validity, and the methods taken to merge the data and created the variables to be used in this study. The data analysis section focused on addressing the details of the data review and cleaning. Last, I will discuss the threats to internal and external validity and the steps taken to minimize these threats, the ethical procedures taken to gain access to the data, and the measures used to protect the participants and the data.

To the extent probable, items from preexisting instruments were used to construct the NNAS (DesRoches et al., 2004; Squillace et al., 2009). In their textbook Lui et al. (2019), validated in identifying the NNAS as one of NCHS' reliable primary source of secondary data that can address healthcare disparities (p.,79). The survey administered by telephone via a computer-assisted telephone interview (CATI) was conducted on average, 40 minutes per call and comprised 11 primary sections: recruitment, education, training and licensure, job history, family life, management and supervision, client relations, organizational commitment, and job

satisfaction; workplace environment, work-related injuries; and demographics (Squillace et al., 2009). The technical advisory panel established content validity of the final instrument with expertise in survey methodology and sample design, long-term care paraprofessional workforce issues, health policy, and evaluation (Squillace et al., 2007).

Data Collection and Management

The 2004 NNAS was administered via telephone using a computer assisted telephone interviewing (CATI) system (Squillace et al., 2006). The content validity of the instrument was established by a technical advisory panel (Squillace et al., 2007). The instrument was tested using a convenience sample of nursing assistants in English (n=9) and Spanish (n=8) to assess the timing, basic comprehension, and flow. It was finalized based upon the findings (Squillace et al., 2006).

Every step of the NNAS was reviewed and approved by the National Center for Health Statistics (NCHS) institutional review board. During the on-site consultation for the NHHS, the nursing facilities provided a list of CNAs who met the eligibility criteria. In addition, the list was reviewed with the facility administrator or proxy to add or remove CNAs. They were deemed ineligible and used a systematic random sampling found within the CATI program to select a sample of CNAs within each sampled facility (Squillace et al., 2009).

Variables and Operational Definitions

Turnover intention

For research questions 1-5, the variable TURNOVER INTENTION was used from the questionnaire to represent turnover intention. In this study, turnover intention is the criterion variable. To examine the relationships between turnover intention and the CNA's structural empowerment, turnover intention was measured using a single item from the NNAS questionnaire: "Is NA currently looking for different job, either as a NA or something else?" The item required participants to answer the question using these options: 1 = yes, 2 = no, 3 = thinking about it. In this study, the cases for the third response ($n = 120$) were removed, changing the variable into a dichotomous variable (0 = No, 1 = Yes).

Like Beecroft, Dorey, & Wenten's (2008) study, turnover intention was measured using a single-item scale. Most turnover studies have looked at single factors associated with turnover, but a few have also conducted multivariate analyses (Castle, 2006; The Lewin Group, 2008; Stearns & D'Arcy, 2008). Many studies on worker turnover behaviors have indicated age, gender, tenure, designation, experience, wages and benefits, education, workplace bullying, and employment industry are predictors of turnover intentions (Bishop et al., 2009; Choi & Johantgen, 2012; Kaur 2013; Zaeri & Rad, 2017). In their study, Cai and Zhou (2009) found structural empowerment and job satisfaction negatively related to turnover intention. However, Hauck et al. (2011) were the first to demonstrate a relationship between structural empowerment and turnover intention among critical care nurses.

Structural empowerment

The variable of structural empowerment represents a multifaceted work environment structures consisting of four dimensions 1) *opportunities* chances for engaging and challenging work and ability to grow professionally; 2) *support* delivery of constructive feedback and assistance from CNA's supervisor, peers, and subordinates; 3) *information* access to organizational policies, procedures, goals, and values, and 4) *resources* time necessary to complete their tasks, and have the equipment, supplies, and tools necessary to complete their assigned tasks.

Opportunities

To operationalize "opportunities," these four items from the NNAS were summed and averaged together: CHALLENGE, NEWSKILL, TRUSTED, and TEAMWORK. The four items required participants to answer the question using a four-point Likert type scale (e.g., 1 = strongly disagree to 4 = strongly agree), so scores for this dimension will range between 1 and 4, with higher scores indicating stronger access to opportunity, and thus, more structural empowerment.

Support

"Support" will be operationalized using these six items: SUPACTS, SUPHELP, SUPADVANCE, SUPTEAM, SUPOPEN, and SUPHEAR. The six items required participants to answer the question using a four-point Likert type scale (e.g., 1 = strongly disagree to 4 =

strongly agree), so scores for this dimension will range between 1 and 4, with higher scores indicating stronger access to support, and thus, more structural empowerment.

Resources

Lastly, to operationalize “resources,” the following two items were aggregated: ASKNA and ASKSTAFF. The four items required participants to answer the question using a four-point Likert scale (e.g., 1 = never to 4 = frequently), so scores for this dimension will range between 1 and 4, with higher scores indicating stronger access to resources, and thus, more structural empowerment.

Information

To operationalize “information,” SUPCLEAR and SUPTELLS were summed and aggregated to operationalize the dimension. The two items required participants to answer the question using a four-point Likert type scale (e.g., 1 = strongly disagree to 4 = strongly agree), so scores for this dimension will range between 1 and 4, with higher scores indicating stronger access to information, and thus, more structural empowerment.

Overall structural empowerment

Overall structural empowerment was measured using a 14-item instrument. An overall structural empowerment score was calculated by summing the scores of the four subscales. The score ranged between 4 and 16. Higher scores signified stronger perceptions of working in an empowered work environment. Scores ranging from 4 and 7 are defined as having low levels of empowerment in the work environment. Scores ranging from 8 to 12 exemplified moderate

levels of empowerment. High levels of empowerment are revealed in scores ranging from 13 to 16 (see Table 2).

Table 2.

Structural Empowerment Subscale Summary.

Construct Measured	Scoring	Likert Scale Range	# Of items	Score Range
Total Structural Empowerment (4 subscales)				
Access to opportunity	Sum of items divided by # of items	1 = strongly disagree to 4 = strongly agree	4	1 to 4
Access to Support	Sum of items divided by # of items	1 = strongly disagree to 4 = strongly agree	6	1 to 4
Access to Resources	Sum of items divided by # of items	1 = never to 4 = frequently	2	1 to 4
Access to information	Sum of items divided by # of items	1 = strongly disagree to 4 = strongly agree	2	1 to 4
			14	4 to 16

Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction denotes to an individual's emotional evaluative reaction to their job. It is an encouraging mentality that stems from having a favorable self-appraisal of job experiences (Locke, 1976). The variable, JOSSATIS, was used to measure the CNA's job satisfaction. The responses to the JOSSATIS survey item, "How satisfied are you with your job?" were analyzed. The response options consisted of 1 = extremely dissatisfied, 2 = somewhat dissatisfied, 3 = somewhat satisfied, 4 = extremely satisfied.

Age

For RQ 7, AGE, consists of ages 16-65 for the participants.

Citizenship status

The variable, CITIZEN, was used to measure citizenship status (0 = no, 1 = yes). Table 3 presents the level of measurement of the nominal, ordinal, and binary variables used for each research question.

Table 3.

Study's Variables

Variable type	Variable	Level of Measurement	<i>n</i>	M	SD	Range
Predictor 1	Opportunities	Ordinal	2604	3.39	.599	1 - 4
Predictor 2	Support	Ordinal	2604	3.27	.748	1 - 4
Predictor 3	Resources	Ordinal	2604	2.60	.718	1 - 4
Predictor 4	Information	Ordinal	2604	3.31	.829	1 - 4
Predictor 5	Structural Empowerment	Scale	2604	12.57	2.047	4.75 - 16
Predictor 6	Job Satisfaction	Ordinal	2604	3.06	.784	1 - 4
Criterion	Turnover Intention	Dichotomous	2604	1.27	.442	1 - 2
Covariate -1	Age	Ratio	2604	36.69	12.58	16 - 65
Covariate -2	Citizenship	Nominal	2604	.07	.247	1 - 2

Data Analysis Plan

The NNAS data zip file, consisting of the original study's source files (original study's methodology, data codebook, SAS, SPSS, and STATA files, was downloaded from NCHS's website (National Center for Health Statistics, 2015). The CSV file (comma-separated value file) was extracted and saved to an external hard drive. Due to the size of the file and limited personal characteristics, only the study's variables were copied to an excel spreadsheet and saved to the

external hard drive. The file was then exported into SPSS for the initial data cleaning process (see Chapter 4).

To examine research question number 1-5, the Cochran-Armitage trend test for association was proposed for the analyses. The Cochran-Armitage trend test for association is used to determine if there is a linear trend between an ordinal independent variable and a dichotomous dependent variable (Laerd Statistics, 2018). SPSS Statistics does not offer a function for running the Cochran-Armitage test of trend (Laerd Statistics, 2018). However, the test results can be obtained by running a binary logistic regression.

According to Agresti (2013), this substitution is fitting because the Cochran-Armitage trend test for association equals the score statistics for testing a single continuous independent variable in a binary logistic regression model. In such case, the researcher used the binary logistic regression method in SPSS statistics to produce the result of the Cochran-Armitage test of trend. To detect a linear trend, the researcher assigned scores to the levels of the ordinal variable (Laerd Statistics, 2018). According to Cochran (1954), selection of scores will not affect the validity of the significance test given they are selected before looking at the results. However, such scores' relative spacing will affect the linear trend's strength (Laerd Statistics, 2018).

Binary logistic regression analysis, by design, overcomes many of the restrictive assumptions of linear regression. For example, normality and homoscedasticity of the residuals are not assumed. Binary logistic regression does require there should be no multicollinearity

among the independent variables. Multicollinearity will be assessed by calculating variance inflation factors (VIF). VIF values over 10 will suggest multicollinearity (Menard, 2009). Binary logistic regression models were conducted for all research questions except for research questions 5a and 5b. A three step forward (Wald) binary logistic regression model was conducted. Tables 4 and 5 provide the variables and statistical tests used to analyze each research question.

Table 4.

Bivariate Analyses.

Research Question #	*PV [LoM]	**CV [LoM]	Statistical Test
RQ 1:	Opportunity (PV1) [ordinal]	Turnover Intention (CV) [dichotomous]	Binary logistic regression
RQ 2:	Support (PV2) [ordinal]	Turnover Intention (CV) [dichotomous]	Binary logistic regression
RQ 3:	Information (PV3) [ordinal]	Turnover Intention (CV) [dichotomous]	Binary logistic regression
RQ 4:	Resources (PV4) [ordinal]	Turnover Intention (CV) [dichotomous]	Binary logistic regression

Note: RQ= research question, LOM= level of measurement, PV= predictor variable, CV= criterion variable

Table 5. Multivariate Analyses

Research Question #	*PV [LoM]	**CV [LoM]	Statistical Test
RQ 5: Do structural empowerment and job satisfaction predict turnover intention?	Structural empowerment (PV5) [Interval] Job Satisfaction (PV6) [Ordinal]	Turnover Intention (CV) [dichotomous]	Binary Regression
RQ 5a: Controlling for age, does structural empowerment predict turnover intention?	Age Covariate-1 [Nominal] Structural empowerment (PV5) [Interval]	Turnover Intention (CV) [dichotomous]	Stepwise Binary logistic regression
RQ 5b: Controlling for citizenship status, does structural empowerment predict turnover intention?	Citizenship Status Covariate-2 [Nominal] Structural empowerment (PV5) [Interval]	Turnover Intention (CV) [dichotomous]	Stepwise Binary logistic regression

Note: RQ= research question, LOM= level of measurement, PV= predictor variable, CV= criterion variable

Assumptions, Limitations, and Delimitations

Assumptions

Creswell (1994) states, “for any given research investigation, there are underlying assumptions, limitations, and delimitations. Assumptions, limitations, and delimitations are considered vital components of a feasible research proposal (Leedy & Ormrod, 2005). The design of this study came with several assumptions. In using a secondary data source: It is assumed the survey participants answered the questions truthfully.

The participant inclusion criteria of the sample are suitable, and all participants have received the same treatment in the data collection process, participants have a genuine interest in

participating the survey instrument (NNAS) and were not influenced to participation using methods outside of the compensation stated in the archival data description.

Limitations

Using archival cross-sectional survey data, the measures for the study have limitations. The data was collected at one period unlike data collected over longer period of times with longitudinal studies, so the results did not measure the effect of change in any of the predictor variables.

The most recent data collection of secondary data source used in this study is from 2004 and poses history bias (Doolan et al., 2017). However, in the most recent use of the data, Han et al. (2014) investigated the associations among state level regulations, initial training quality and focus, and job satisfaction in certified nursing assistants. They found that CNAs who received additional initial training were more likely to report that their training was high quality, which is related to job satisfaction. Job satisfaction has been linked to nursing home turnover, indicating awareness to training may improve satisfaction and decrease staff turnover (Han et al., 2014). History bias may pose a problem. The participants in the survey are anonymous in accordance the original consent agreement. Therefore, opportunities for follow-up or the collection of additional data from the participants is a limitation in furthering this research (Johnston, 2013).

The study's observational correlational research design is another limitation. With this research design, the researcher observes the phenomena and measures whatever relationships exist, without manipulating the predictor variables in the study. In addition, because of

directionality and third (confounding) variable problems, correlational study designs cannot imply causation between the predictor and outcome variables, adding to the limitations of the study's research design (Creswell, 1994).

Delimitations

The delimitations of a study are the characteristics that may arise from the limitations in the study or the boundaries and parameters of the study (Simon & Goes, 2013). The delimitations goals are to narrow the scope of the study. This study presented restrictions with using archival data. The delimitations of this study were: (1) the studying the relationship between the four subscales of structural empowerment, citizenship status, and turnover intention in certified nursing assistants assessed in the original survey, (3) performing secondary data analysis, the researcher had no control over the survey questions and had to build the study's questions around the pre-collected survey data collected, (4) despite it being a common practice for researchers to answer new research questions using existing (Doolan et al., 2017) data sets, there's not a lot of publications that guide this type of research, (5) the use of closed ended Likert scale responses in the archival data, (6) another delimitating factor for this research was the period in which the cross-sectional data collection occurred, and (7) the participants currently working as CNAs for six months or more will be included in the study.

Ethical Assurances

The confidentiality of data is not only a critical component in social research, but also specifically imperative when data gathered for a particular purpose are provided for use by the

public (Cheng & Phillips, 2014). Necessary safeguards are required to ensure participants remain anonymous (restricting public access to participants names and addresses, withholding geographical location information, and/or minimizing any certain or uncommon characteristics that would enable a respondent to be uniquely revealed (Cheng & Phillips, 2014).

The NNAS survey results are public information and available online, the contact information was retrieved from the NCHS website (CDC/National Center for Health Statistics, 2010). The appropriate department representative was contacted via telephone to notify of the intent to use the 2004 NNAS Survey data. Because secondary data from a free and public use website was used, no compensation or contact with human subjects was involved. On October 1, 2020, the Institutional Review Board (IRB) application was submitted for review and concurrence. Approval from the IRB of Trident University International to conduct the study was received on October 12, 2020 (IRB # 1186).

The data file included encrypted individual nursing assistant and facility identifiers. Access to the real identifiers of the study's participants was not available nor accessible. While this study's scope is outside of Trident University International and the results will be published, this study encompasses no human subjects, which met the requirements for exemption under 45CFR 46.101 (b) and exemption in the application for IRB review.

Summary

In this chapter, the researcher justified the selection of a quantitative, nonexperimental design. In addition, the researcher discussed the population, sampling frame, and data collection

procedures of the secondary data source. The archival data and variables of interest were operationally defined. The chapter ended with a data analysis plan, threats to validity, and ethical considerations. In the next chapter, the researcher will present the data analysis findings. Descriptive statistics was run to explore trends of the sample. Inferential analyses were used to statistically report the research questions.

Chapter IV: Results

The purpose of this correlational quantitative study was to measure the four dimensions of structural empowerment, job satisfaction, citizenship, and investigate their association with turnover intention in multigenerational CNAs, who work in nursing homes across the U.S. In addition, this study aimed to contribute to the knowledge base by understanding how CNAs, employed in skilled nursing facilities, work environments affect their turnover intention. This chapter discusses the study's secondary data analysis and statistical tests used to conduct them accordingly.

Data Screening and Cleaning

For this analysis, data from the 2004 NNAS, was analyzed to answer the research questions. The data was nonidentifiable and accessible by the public. The dataset files were retrieved from NCHS website and saved onto the researcher's external hard drive. The files provided the survey methodology, questionnaire, data dictionaries, and data files. The data set was available in SPSS, SAS, and Text_ASCII versions. The data set was imported into SPSS 28 and exported and saved as a password protected excel file on the researcher's hard drive for backup purposes.

Missing data

Before running the inferential analyses, the dataset was screened for missing data and outliers. SPSS automatically used listwise deletion in the removal of partial responses. In addition, this step provided information on the profile of missing data for each variable. It was

important for the researcher to know the missing values for each variable to make the best decision on how to code the study's variables. The researcher recoded the original variables to properly handle the missing values and if needed, transform the distribution of the variables to meet assumptions of the proposed statistical models used in the study. Cheng and Phillips, (2014) states all recoded variables should be stored in a new dataset as well as documenting all syntax for the recoding of the variables.

There was a total of 3,017 observations in the NNAS survey instrument. Participants with missing data for the key variables, were removed. There were $n = 293$ observations removed, when the subscale scores for the predictor variables (Opportunity, Support, Resources, and Information) were calculated for purposes of the data analysis. An additional $n = 120$ cases were removed when the third category of the criterion variable, Turnover Intention, was collapsed into a dichotomous variable. The final analyses were conducted used a sample of $n = 2,604$ subjects.

In consideration of the design of the original study (2007) the current study's data analysis was modified to create less biased estimates (Cheng & Phillips, 2014; Squillace et al., 2007). The reliability coefficients of each dimension of structural empowerment were calculated using Cronbach's alpha coefficient before analyses are conducted to answer the research questions. The analytical techniques used in the data analysis includes descriptive statistics and binary logistic regression.

Descriptive Statistics

Participants

The sample population consisted of 2,604 CNAs working in skilled nursing facilities across the U.S. The participants' ages ranged from 16 years to 65 years. The median age of the participants from the NNAS was 36.69 (see Tables 6). Today, the median age for CNAs is 38 (Paraprofessional Health Institute, 2021). Participants identified as female ($n = 2405$) encompassed 92% of the sample (see figure 2). For marital status, married was the most represented category ($n = 1,025$). Representing 93.47% of the sample, an overwhelming majority of the participants were U.S. citizens ($n = 2,434$).

Figure 2.

Gender Distributions

Table 6.*Study's Variable Descriptives*

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
SEX		
Female	2405	92%
Male	199	8%
Citizenship status		
U.S. citizens	2434	93.47%
Non-U.S. citizens	170	2%
Race		
Black	833	32%
White	1586	61%
Other	69	3%
Asian	116	4%
Marital status		
Married	1025	39%
Living with partner	303	12%
Separated	151	6%
Divorced	312	12%
Widowed	95	4%
Never married	715	28%
Refused	2	0.08%
Not Ascertained	1	0.04%
Level of education		
1-11 years	729	30%
High school	1192	46%
Some college	537	21%
College graduate	88	3%
Post college	12	0.46%
Bed size		
0-49 beds	372	14%
50-99 beds	1009	39%
100-199 beds	1082	42%
200+	141	5%
Ownership type		
For-profit	1535	59%
All others (private, gov't, not-for-profit)	1069	41%

Study's Variables

Descriptive statistics were calculated for the study's variables. See these findings in Table 7.

Table 7.

Study's Variables Descriptives

Variable type	Variable	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>range</i>
Predictor 1	Opportunities	2604	3.39	.599	1-4
Predictor 2	Support	2604	3.27	.748	1-4
Predictor 3	Resources	2604	2.60	.718	1-4
Predictor 4	Information	2604	3.31	.829	1-4
Predictor 5	Structural Empowerment	2604	12.57	2.047	4.75-16
Predictor 6	Job Satisfaction	2604	3.06	.784	1-4
Criterion	Turnover Intention	2604	1.27	.442	1-2
Covariate -1	Age	Ratio	2604	36.69	12.58
Covariate -2	Citizenship	Nominal	2604	.07	.247

Structural Empowerment

Of the four subscales of structural empowerment, CNAs perceived access to opportunities ($M = 3.39$) more than access to support, resources, and information, close to Chunfeng and Zhou (2009) findings. The mean score for structural empowerment was 12.57, indicating a moderate level of empowerment perceived by the participants and are in alignment with Al Sabei et al. (2022).

With skewness levels of each subscale less than 2, none of the subscales had asymmetrical means. None of the subscales had kurtosis levels greater than or equal to 3. This indicates the subscales' distribution is markedly different than a normal distribution in its tendency to produce outliers (Westfall & Henning, 2013). See Table 8 for the summary descriptive for structural empowerment and its subscales.

Table 8.*Structural Empowerment and Its Subscales Summary*

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>SE_M</i>	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
Opportunities	3.39	0.60	2604	0.01	1.00	4.00	-1.15	1.13
Information	3.31	0.83	2604	0.02	1.00	4.00	-1.12	0.36
Support	3.27	0.75	2604	0.01	1.00	4.00	-1.09	0.44
Resources	2.60	0.72	2604	0.01	1.00	4.00	0.07	-0.56
Structural Empowerment	12.57	2.05	2604	0.04	4.75	16.00	-0.84	0.36

Note. '-' indicates the statistic is undefined due to constant data or an insufficient sample size.

Turnover Intention

The criterion variable, Turnover Intention, a dichotomous variable, was coded 0 = No and 1 = Yes. The variable had a mean of 1.25 (SD = .442), with the No category ($n = 1910$) being the most frequently observed at 73.3% of the participants.

Job Satisfaction

The predictor variable Job Satisfaction, measured on a 4-point Likert type scale, had a mean score of 3.06, indicating the CNAs were somewhat satisfied. The most frequently observed category of Job Satisfaction was 3 ($n = 1325$, 50.88%).

Citizenship

For citizenship, the most frequently observed category, was U.S. citizens, See Table 9 for descriptive summary.

Table 9.*Frequency Table of Ordinal and Nominal Variables*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
JOSSATIS		
Extremely dissatisfied	111	4.26
Somewhat dissatisfied	392	15.05
Somewhat satisfied	1325	50.88
Extremely satisfied	776	29.80
Turnover Intention		
No	1910	73.35
Yes	694	26.65
Citizenship		
Non-U.S. citizens	170	6.53%
U.S. citizens	2434	93.47%

Age

The observations for age mean are 36.69 ($SD = 12.58$, $SE_M = 0.25$, Min = 16.00, Max = 65.00, Skewness = 0.37, Kurtosis = -0.87). When the skewness is greater than 2 in absolute value, the variable is considered asymmetrical about its mean. When the kurtosis is greater than or equal to 3, the variable's distribution is markedly different from a normal distribution in its tendency to produce outliers (Westfall & Henning, 2013). The descriptive statistics for age are indicated in Table 10.

Table 10.*Summary Statistics for Age*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>SE_M</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>Skewness</i>	<i>Kurtosis</i>
AGE	36.69	12.58	2604	0.25	16.00	65.00	0.37	-0.87

Correlation Matrix of the Structural Empowerment Subscales

A Pearson correlation analysis was conducted among information, opportunity, resources, support, and structural empowerment. Cohen's standard was used to evaluate the strength of the relationships, where coefficients between .10 and .29 represent a small effect size, coefficients between .30 and .49 represent a moderate effect size, and coefficients above .50 indicate a large effect size (Cohen, 1988). A statistically significant correlation does not inevitably indicate a strong correlation (Akoglu, 2018). A significant positive correlation was observed between all subscales except for the relationships between information and resources and resources and support (see Table 11). The result of the correlations was examined using the Holm correction to adjust for multiple comparisons based on an alpha value of .05 and a 95.00% CI.

Table 11.

Correlation Matrix of the Structural Empowerment Subscales

Pearson Correlation coefficient <i>n</i> = 2,604					
Pearson's Correlation Coefficient	Opportunity	Support	Information	Resources	Structural Empowerment
Opportunity	1.000	<i>r</i> = 0.52, <i>p</i> < .001,	<i>r</i> = 0.45, <i>p</i> < .001	<i>r</i> = 0.10, <i>p</i> < .001	<i>r</i> = 0.70, <i>p</i> < .001
Support	<i>r</i> = 0.52, <i>p</i> < .001	1.000	<i>r</i> = 0.77 <i>p</i> < .001,	<i>r</i> = 0.06, <i>p</i> < .010	<i>r</i> = 0.85, <i>p</i> < .001
Information	<i>r</i> = 0.45, <i>p</i> < .001	<i>r</i> = 0.77, <i>p</i> < .001,	1.000	<i>r</i> = 0.04, <i>p</i> < .032	<i>r</i> = 0.83, <i>p</i> < .001
Resources	<i>r</i> = .10, <i>p</i> < .001	<i>r</i> = 0.06, <i>p</i> < .010	<i>r</i> = 0.04, <i>p</i> < .032	1.000	<i>r</i> = 0.42 <i>p</i> < .001

Structural	$r = 0.70,$	$r = 0.85,$	$r = 0.83,$	$r = 0.42,$	1.000
Empowerment	$p < .001$	$p < .001$	$p < .001$	$p < .001$	

Data Analysis Results

Bivariate Analyses

Statistical Test Assumptions

In this study, logistic regression models were run to test the hypothesis and answer the research questions. Unlike linear regression, logistic regression does not require a linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables. However, logistic regression does require the independent variables and the logit odds of the dependent variable be linearly related. The dichotomous outcomes for turnover intention, the dependent variable in the study, meets this requirement. Another logistic regression assumption is for the observations to be independent of each other and for there to be little or no multicollinearity among them. To check for multicollinearity, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) tests were run for each model. Logistic regression does not require the residuals of the models to be normally distributed or have a constant variance, also known as homoscedasticity (Schreiber-Gregory et al., 2018). Logistic regression does require the dependent variable to not be measured on an interval or ratio scale. Turnover intention, the criterion variable in the study, was analyzed using binary logistic regressions models due to its binary characteristics. Lastly, logistic regression requires large sample sizes or for the total number observations should be more than 500 (Bujang and Baharum, 2016).

Data Screening

Descriptive statistics were first examined to explore the trends of the sample. Binary logistic regressions were used to address the research questions. Statistical significance was evaluated at the generally accepted level, $\alpha = .05$.

Based upon the dichotomous level of measurement for the criterion variable, Turnover Intention, binary logistic regression will be used to answer research questions 1 to 5. Prior to running the data analyses, the following assumptions were checked: (a) the dependent (criterion) variable must be dichotomous, (b) there are one or more independent variables (predictor) that are either continuous or nominal variables, (c) there are independence of observations, (d) the dichotomous categories of the dependent (criterion) variable and all nominal independent (predictor) variables are mutually exclusive and exhaustive, and (e) there are a minimum of 15 cases per independent (predictor) variable. In addition, the assumption of absence of multicollinearity was examined.

Research Question 1

Do access to opportunity significantly predict CNA turnover intention?

Opportunity

Bivariate analyses were performed to explore the relationships between the predictor variables, opportunity and the criterion variable, turnover intention. A binary logistic regression was conducted to examine whether opportunity significantly affected the odds of observing the No category of turnover intention. The reference category for turnover intention was *Yes*.

The model was evaluated based on an alpha of .05. The overall model was significant, $\chi^2(1) = 143.24, p < .001$, suggesting opportunity had a significant effect on the odds of observing the Yes category of turnover intention. McFadden's R-squared was calculated to examine the model fit, where values greater than .2 are indicative of models with excellent fit (Louviere et al., 2000). The overall model fit was $R^2 = 0.05$, which means 1% of the variance of turnover intention levels was explained by the included predictor. The effect of opportunity was significant, $B = -0.86, OR = 0.42, p < .001$, indicating that for a one-unit increase in opportunity, decrease the odds of observing the Yes category of turnover intention by approximately 57.70%. Since access to opportunity is significant in the regression model, the null hypothesis (H_{a1}) was rejected. Table 12 summarizes the results of the regression model.

Table 12.

Opportunity Predicting Turnover Intention Results

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	χ^2	<i>p</i>	<i>OR</i>	95.00% CI
(Intercept)	1.85	0.24	57.34	< .001	-	-
Opportunity	-0.86	0.07	137.99	< .001	0.42	[0.37, 0.49]

Note. $\chi^2(1) = 143.24, p < .001, McFadden R^2 = 0.05$.

Research Question 2

RQ2: Do access to support significantly predict CNA turnover intention?

Support

Bivariate analyses were performed to explore the relationships between the predictor variables, support and the criterion variable, turnover intention. A binary logistic regression was

conducted to examine whether support significantly affected the odds of observing the *No* category of turnover intention. The reference category for turnover intention was *Yes*.

The model was evaluated based on an alpha of .05. The overall model was significant, $\chi^2(1) = 151.91, p < .001$, suggesting support had a significant effect on the odds of observing the *Yes* category of turnover intention. McFadden's R-squared was calculated to examine the model fit, where values greater than .2 are indicative of models with excellent fit (Louviere et al., 2000). The overall model fit was $R^2 = 0.05$, which means 1% of the variance of turnover intention levels was explained by the included predictor. The effect of support was significant, $B = -0.71, OR = 0.49, p < .001$, indicating that for a one-unit increase in support, decrease the odds of observing the *Yes* category of turnover intention would increase by approximately 50.72%. Since support is significant in the regression model, the null hypothesis (H_{a2}) was rejected. Table 13 summarizes the results of the regression model.

Table 13.

Support Predicting Turnover Intention Regression Results

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	χ^2	<i>p</i>	<i>OR</i>	95.00% CI
(Intercept)	1.25	0.19	44.13	< .001	-	-
Support	-0.71	0.06	148.00	< .001	0.49	[0.44, 0.55]

Note. $\chi^2(1) = 151.91, p < .001, McFadden R^2 = 0.05$.

Research Question 3

Do access to information significantly predict CNA turnover intention?

Information

Bivariate analyses were performed to explore the relationships between the predictor variables, information and the criterion variable, turnover intention. A binary logistic regression was conducted to examine whether information significantly affected the odds of observing the *No* category of turnover intention. The reference category for turnover intention was *Yes*.

The model was evaluated based on an alpha of .05. The overall model was significant, $\chi^2(1) = 122.35, p < .001$, suggesting information had a significant effect on the odds of observing the *Yes* category of turnover intention. McFadden's R-squared was calculated to examine the model fit, where values greater than .2 are indicative of models with excellent fit (Louviere et al., 2000). The overall model fit was $R^2 = 0.04$, which means 1% of the variance of turnover intention levels was explained by the included predictor. The effect of information was significant, $B = -0.57, OR = 0.57, p < .001$, indicating that for a one-unit increase in information, decrease the odds of observing the *Yes* category of turnover intention would increase by approximately 43.43%. Since information is significant in the regression model, the null hypothesis (H_{a3}) was rejected. Table 14 summarizes the results of the regression model.

Table 14.

Information Predicting Turnover Intention Regression Results

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	χ^2	<i>p</i>	<i>OR</i>	95.00% CI
(Intercept)	0.82	0.17	23.65	< .001	-	-
Information	-0.57	0.05	121.21	< .001	0.57	[0.51, 0.63]

Note. $\chi^2(1) = 122.35, p < .001, McFadden R^2 = 0.04$.

Research Question 4

Do access to resources significantly predict CNA turnover intention?

Resources

Bivariate analyses were performed to explore the relationships between the predictor variables, resources and the criterion variable, turnover intention. A binary logistic regression was conducted to examine whether resources significantly affected the odds of observing the No category of turnover intention. The reference category for turnover intention was Yes.

The model was evaluated based on an alpha of .05. The overall model was not significant, $\chi^2(1) = 1.78$, $p = .182$, suggesting Resources did not have a significant effect on the odds of observing the Yes category of turnover intention. McFadden's R-squared was calculated to examine the model fit, where values greater than .2 are indicative of models with excellent fit (Louviere et al., 2000). The overall model fit was $R^2 = 0.00$.

Since access to resources was not significant in the regression model, the individual predictor was not examined further, causing a failure to reject the null hypothesis (H_{a4}). Table 15 summarizes the results of the regression model.

Table 15.

Resources Predicting Turnover Intention Regression Results

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	χ^2	<i>p</i>	<i>OR</i>	95% CI
(Intercept)	-0.80	0.17	23.32	< .001	-	-
Resources	-0.08	0.06	1.78	.183	0.92	[0.82, 1.04]

Note. $\chi^2(1) = 1.02$, $p < .312$, McFadden $R^2 = 0.0003$.

Multivariate Analyses

Research Question 5

Does structural empowerment and job satisfaction significantly predict CNA turnover intention?

Structural Empowerment

In a binary logistic regression model, structural empowerment and job satisfaction were examined to determine if there was a significant effect on the odds of observing the Yes category of turnover intention. The reference category for turnover intention was No.

The overall model was evaluated based on an alpha of .05 and was significant, $\chi^2(2) = 377.55, p < .001$, suggesting that structural empowerment and job satisfaction, had a significant effect on the odds of observing the Yes category of turnover intention. McFadden's R-squared was calculated to examine the model fit, where values greater than .2 are indicative of models with excellent fit (Louviere et al., 2000). The McFadden R-squared value calculated for this model was 0.13.

The effect of structural empowerment was significant, $B = -0.12$, $OR = 0.89, p < .001$, indicating that a one-unit increase in structural empowerment decrease the odds of observing the Yes category of turnover intention by approximately 11.36%, rejecting the null hypothesis (H_{a5}).

The effect of job satisfaction was significant, $B = -.97$, $OR = 0.38, p < .001$, indicating that a one-unit increase in job satisfaction decrease the odds of observing the Yes category of

turnover intention by approximately 62.04%, rejecting the null hypothesis (H_{a6}). Table 16 summarizes the results of the regression model.

Table 16.

Research Question 5 Regression Results

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	χ^2	<i>p</i>	<i>OR</i>	95% CI
(Intercept)	3.32	0.30	126.09	< .001	-	-
Structural Empowerment	-0.12	0.03	22.82	< .001	0.89	[0.84, 0.93]
Job Satisfaction	-0.97	0.07	185.72	< .001	0.38	[0.33, 0.44]

Note. $\chi^2(2) = 377.55, p < .001, \text{McFadden } R^2 = 0.13.$

Research Questions 5a

Controlling for age, does structural empowerment significantly predict turnover intention?

To address research questions 5a, age was added first in a stepwise binary logistic model containing predictors, structural empowerment, job satisfaction, and the criterion variable, turnover intention, in which it was evaluated at an alpha of .05. The overall model was significant, $\chi^2(3) = 413.591, p < .001$, suggesting that job satisfaction, structural empowerment, and age had a significant effect on the odds of observing the Yes category of turnover intention. The model chi-square test results indicate the overall model is significant fit relative to the structural empowerment regression model in Table 17. McFadden's R-squared was performed to observe the model fit, where values greater than .2 are suggestive of models with excellent fit (Louviere et al., 2000). The McFadden R-squared value computed for this model was 0.14.

The effect of age was significant, $B = -0.02$, $OR = 0.98$, $p < .001$, indicating that a one-unit increase in age decrease the odds of observing the Yes category of turnover intention by approximately 2.35%.

The effect of the job satisfaction was significant, $B = -0.96$, $OR = 0.38$, $p < .001$, indicating that a one-unit increase in job satisfaction decrease the odds of observing the Yes category of turnover intention by approximately 61.90%.

The effect of the structural empowerment was significant, $B = -0.13$, $OR = 0.88$, $p < .001$, indicating that a one-unit increase in structural empowerment decrease the odds of observing the Yes category of turnover intention by approximately 11.79% (see Table 17).

Table 17.

Structural Empowerment and Job Satisfaction Predicting for Turnover Intention While Controlling for Age

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Constant	4.21	.338	155.086	1	<.001	67.485		
Age	-.024	.004	34.765	1	<.001	.976	.969	.984
Job Satisfaction	-.965	.072	180.193	1	<.001	.381	.331	.439
Structural Empowerment	-.125	.025	24.245	1	<.001	.882	.839	.927

a. Variable(s) entered on step 2: Age, Job Satisfaction, Structural Empowerment.

The participants were group into 5-year age groups to assess their perceived structural empowerment scores. As previously mentioned in Chapter 3, structural empowerment was scored from 4 to 16 using summated aggregated data from the structural empowerment dimensions, opportunity, support, resources, and information. The structural empowerment scores were categorized into three groups, low level (4 to 7), moderate level (8 to 12), and high level (13 to 16). While few CNAs perceived low levels of structural empowerment, CNAs age

31 to 35 experienced the highest levels amongst the age groups. CNAs, age 21 to 25, perceived the highest moderate (8 to 12) (41.35%) and high level (13 to 16) (57.08%) of structural empowerment. In a crosstab analysis assessing the CNAs' structural empowerment levels age groups, the CNAs experienced high levels of perceived structural empowerment across all age groups. See Table 18 for this cross-tabulation analysis.

Table 18.*Frequency Table for Ordinal Variables*

Variable	Age Groups									
	16-20	21-25	26-30	31-35	36-40	41-45	46-50	51-55	56-60	61-65
Structural Empowerment levels										
Low (4-7)	3 (1.35%)	3 (0.71%)	8 (2.35%)	12 (3.74%)	7 (2.41%)	4 (1.23%)	7 (2.79%)	7 (3.52%)	1 (0.76%)	0 (0.00%)
Moderate (8-12)	77 (34.68%)	179 (42.22%)	141 (41.35%)	137 (42.68%)	106 (36.55%)	125 (38.58%)	90 (35.86%)	58 (29.15%)	42 (32.06%)	38 (37.62%)
High (13-16)	142 (63.96%)	242 (57.08%)	192 (56.30%)	172 (53.58%)	177 (61.03%)	195 (60.19%)	154 (61.35%)	134 (67.34%)	88 (67.18%)	63 (62.38%)

Research Questions 5b

To address research question 5b, citizenship was added first in a stepwise binary logistic model containing predictors, structural empowerment, job satisfaction, and the criterion variable, turnover intention, in which it was evaluated at an alpha of .05. The overall model was significant, $\chi^2(3) = 381.87$, $p < .001$, suggesting that job satisfaction, structural empowerment, and citizenship had a significant effect on the odds of observing the Yes category of turnover intention. The model chi-square test results indicate the overall model is significant fit relative to the structural empowerment regression model in Table 19. McFadden's R-squared was performed to observe the model fit, where values greater than .2 are suggestive of models with excellent fit (Louviere et al., 2000). The McFadden R-squared value computed for this model was 0.13.

The effect of the non-U.S. citizen category of citizenship was significant, $B = -0.39$, $OR = 0.67$, $p = .034$, indicating that observing the non-U.S. citizen category of citizenship decreases the odds of observing the Yes category of turnover intention by approximately 32.58% relative to the U.S. citizen category of citizenship.

The effect of structural empowerment was significant, $B = -0.12$, $OR = 0.88$, $p < .001$, indicating that a one-unit increase in structural empowerment decrease the odds of observing the Yes category of structural empowerment by approximately 11.57%.

The effect of the job satisfaction was significant, $B = -0.97$, $OR = 0.38$, $p < .001$, indicating that a one-unit increase in job satisfaction decrease the odds of observing the Yes category of turnover intention by approximately 62.18% (see Table 19).

Table 19.

Logistic Regression Results with Structural Empowerment, Citizenship, and Job Satisfaction Predicting Turnover Intention

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	χ^2	<i>p</i>	<i>OR</i>	95.00% CI
(Intercept)	3.72	0.35	110.46	< .001	-	-
Structural Empowerment	-0.12	0.03	23.60	< .001	0.88	[0.84, 0.93]
Citizenship (1)	-0.39	0.19	4.48	.034	0.67	[0.47, 0.97]
Job Satisfaction	-0.97	0.07	186.54	< .001	0.38	[0.33, 0.43]

Note. $\chi^2(3) = 381.87$, $p < .001$, McFadden $R^2 = 0.13$.

Summary

This chapter provided the results of the secondary data analysis in testing the research questions. Findings for the binary logistic regressions indicated significant effects between structural empowerment, job satisfaction, and citizenship and turnover intention. However, when each structural empowerment subscale was analyzed with turnover intention, all subscales had a significant effect on the Yes category of turnover intention, except for resources. With these findings, I was able to reject all the study's null hypotheses, except for the fourth null hypotheses (see Table 20 for the hypotheses summary). Chapter 5 will continue to discuss the findings and linking the results to the knowledgebase, limitations of the study, implications of the study and recommendations for future research.

Table 20.*Hypotheses Summary*

Hypothesis	Probability Value	Results
Ha1: Access to opportunity significantly do not predict turnover intention	$p < .001$	Reject null hypothesis
Ha2: Access to support significantly do not predict turnover intention	$p < .001$	Reject null hypothesis
Ha3: Access to information significantly do not predict turnover intention	$p < .001$	Reject null hypothesis
Ha4: Access to resources significantly do not predict turnover intention	$p = .183$	Fail to reject null hypothesis
Ha5: Structural empowerment significantly do not predict turnover intention	$p < .001$	Reject null hypothesis
Ha6: Job satisfaction significantly do not predict turnover intention	$p < .001$	Reject null hypothesis

Chapter V: Discussion and Conclusion

1.5 million nursing assistants are working in the U.S. healthcare system (Staff Writers, 2020). While most are helping fill critical roles in nursing care facilities, others work with home healthcare agencies, hospitals, and assisted living facilities. Poor job quality and work environments continue to raise turnover and increase job vacancies in the long-term care industry (PHI, 2020). As the demand for direct care workers in nursing homes continues to rise, greater attention and effort must identify sources to meet the needs of the industry (The Leading Age LTSS Center, 2018).

This correlational quantitative study measured the four dimensions of structural empowerment and job satisfaction and investigate their correlational relationship turnover intention in a multigenerational sample of CNAs, who work in nursing homes across the U.S. Age and citizenship status were studied as predicative factors significantly associated with CNA turnover intention rates. In addition, this study aimed to contribute to the knowledgebase by understanding how CNAs belonging to different age generations and citizenship statuses, employed in skilled nursing facilities, work environments affect their turnover intention.

Using the research questions and hypotheses as a guide, the researcher applied an observational and quantitative correlational research design to conduct secondary data analysis using the 2004 NNAS. The predictor variables consisted of structural empowerment and its four subscales, according to Kanter's structural empowerment theory, and job satisfaction. The

criterion variable in this study was turnover intention. Age and citizenship status were incorporated into the study as control variables.

In this chapter, the study results are discussed that are aligned with the objectives, connecting this information to the knowledge base. The predictors organize the discussion regarding the results analyzed against CNAs' turnover intention. The chapter further discusses the limitations of the research and the implications of the study's findings in relation to policy, practice, and research.

Interpretation of the Findings with the Literature

There were several findings that were of importance in this study.

Research Questions 1-4

For research questions 1 through 4, binary logistic regression analysis was conducted on structural empowerment and turnover intention subscales. Findings for the binary logistic regressions indicated significant associations for all subscales of structural empowerment, except for access to resources. A significant relationship was found among overall structural empowerment and turnover intention. All hypotheses were rejected except for the hypothesis for research question 4. Due to both access to information and access to resources not having a significant association to turnover intention, there was a failure to reject the null hypotheses.

Opportunities and Turnover Intention

While high turnover may be a significant cause for concern, it is also important to understand the related factors. According to the literature, Luo et al. (2007) and Morris, (2009)

indicated the potential for career advancement for workers and the chance for them to cultivate and refine their skills and move up the career ladder to be negatively associated with their intent to leave. These findings followed the current study's findings, in which the researcher found a negative significant relationship between the CNAs access to opportunity and their turnover intention. The more access to opportunities were perceived, the less likely the CNA would leave their job (see Figure 3). However, in their study, McCaughey et al., (2012) found no significant relationship between intent to leave the job and the availability of career ladder jobs in home health agencies. In a study using a random sample of 72 nursing facilities ($N = 1,779$), Bishop et al. (2009) analyzed the responses of 2,252 NAs in the 2004 NNAS to explore their work practices, regarding their wages and work environments, and how both affected the NAs' job satisfaction. Their findings illuminated the significance of the availability of extrinsic rewards such as opportunities for upward career mobility, pay raises and receiving benefit options like health insurance, inferring access to opportunities could be essential in NA retention (Bishop, Squillace, Meagher, Anderson, & Wiener, 2009).

Figure 3.
Access to Opportunity and Turnover Intention Trend

Support and Turnover Intention

Work environments offering support access produces positive patient experiences (Laschinger et al., 2010). However, Cai and Zhou (2009), could not find a positive relationship between structural empowerment, job satisfaction, and turnover intention in their examination of Chinese nurses’ perceived workplace structural empowerment. Ozbozkurt et al. (2021) examined the relationship between structural empowerment and supervisor support of healthcare employees working in private healthcare. In their analysis, they found a strong significant

relationship. These findings aligned with the positive correlational relationship between the CNAs access to support and their turnover intention in the current study, as the more access to support were perceived, the less likely the CNA would leave their job (see Figure 4).

Figure 4.

Access to Support and Turnover Intention Trend.

Examining the levels of workplace structural empowerment of 189 staff nurses from two central China hospitals, Cai et al. (2011) found the nurses perceived moderate levels of workplace structural empowerment to be negatively related to turnover intention. These findings

aligned with Khaled and Zaki (2017) study of nurses in non-critical and critical care departments and Galletta, et. al., (2011). Han et al. (2015) reported that nurses who were planning to leave their job experienced lower autonomy levels and peer support than their nurse counterparts who remained in their positions.

Resources, Information, and Turnover Intention

Resources. Restructuring direct care jobs as a steppingstone to a career in the health care industry will appeal to available labor pools and extend the universe of future job seekers who will consider this occupation. In addition, incumbent workers are likely to stay on the job longer while participating in and completing training that will further advance their careers. Roji & Jooste (2020) referenced nurses having access to information, support, and resources in their work environments made up their power sources. While CNAs in the current study were found to possess lower access to resources, access to information was experienced at higher levels ($M = 3.31$), second highest to access to opportunity, out of the structural empowerment subscales. This supports the statistically significant findings of access to information predicting turnover intention, rejecting H_{03} null hypothesis. Perceived access to resources did not have a significant effect on their turnover intention, leaving the researcher to fail to reject null hypothesis (H_{04}).

Research Question 5

For research question 5, a binary logistic regression indicated job satisfaction and structural empowerment significantly affected turnover intention. Most turnover intention studies have looked at single factors associated with turnover intention, but a few have also conducted

multivariate analyses (Castle, 2006; Karantzas et al., 2012; Stearns & D'Arcy, 2008; The Lewin Group, 2008). Many studies on worker turnover behaviors have indicated age, gender, tenure, designation, experience, wages and benefits, education, workplace bullying, and employment industry are predictors of turnover intentions (Bishop et al., 2009; Choi & Johantgen, 2012; Kaur et al., 2013; Zaeri & Rad, 2017). Hauck et al. (2011) were the first to demonstrate a relationship between structural empowerment and turnover intention among critical care nurses. This counters what Laschinger (2012) found in her study, which found a negative association between structural empowerment and job turnover in first and second-year nurses. Similarly, in their study, Cai & Zhou (2009), Amboy (2018), and Kelly et al. (2022) demonstrated a negative association between structural empowerment and job turnover intention.

Structural Empowerment and Job Satisfaction's Association with Turnover Intention

The structural empowerment scores were recoded from scale to nominal by separating the scores into the following categories: scores ranging from 4 to 7 were categorized as low level of structural empowerment. Scores ranging between 8 and 12 were categorized as moderate level of structural empowerment. Scores between 13 and 16 were coded as high levels of structural empowerment. A strong correlation was found between the cross tabulated measures of structural empowerment and turnover intention. The most frequently observed category of the structural empowerment levels within the No category of turnover intention, was high level of structural empowerment ($n = 1,255, 65.71\%$). The most frequently observed category of structural empowerment levels within the Yes category of turnover intention was moderate level

of structural empowerment ($n = 356, 51.30\%$). Frequencies and percentages are presented in Table 21.

These indications counter the findings of Laschinger (2012), in which a negative association between structural empowerment and job turnover in first- and second-year nurses. Similarly, Cai & Zhou (2009), Galletta & colleagues (2011), and Amboy (2018) indicated a negative association between structural empowerment, job satisfaction, and turnover intention in their studies. However, the study's findings support findings in a study conducted on 65 nurses, from long-term care facilities in Taiwan, psychological and structural empowerment were found to be positively correlated with job satisfaction, with structural empowerment having a mediating effect on job satisfaction (standardized $\beta = 0.46$, Sobel test: $z = 2.69$, $P = 0.007$) (Li et al., 2013).

Table 21.*SE Levels and Turnover Intention Crosstabulations*

Variable	Turnover Intention (TOI)		
	No	Yes	Total
Structural Empowerment (SE)			
low level of structural empowerment	18 (0.94%)	34 (4.90%)	52
moderate level of structural empowerment	637 (33.35%)	356 (51.30%)	993
high level of structural empowerment	1255 (65.71%)	304 (43.80%)	1559
Total	1910 (100.00%)	694 (100.00%)	2604

Note. SE = Structural Empowerment Due to rounding error, percentages may not sum to 100%.

Job satisfaction and turnover intention

Job satisfaction is often measured using multiple items combined to form global job satisfaction. Some studies have used a single form of measurement in assessing job satisfaction (Dolbier et al., 2005; Lepold et al., 2018). Using data from the 2004 NNAS in their research, Choi and Johantgen (2012) used a single measure of job satisfaction in their study on fixed effects of work-related factors and supervisory support and its effects on nursing assistants' retention. Using multilevel logistic regression, they found that personal factors like age, education, and work history were related to intent to leave but not job satisfaction (Choi & Johantgen, 2012).

The most frequently observed job satisfaction category within the No category of turnover intention was Somewhat Satisfied ($n = 994, 52.04\%$). The most frequently observed job satisfaction category within the Yes category of turnover intention was Somewhat Satisfied ($n = 331, 47.69\%$). A strong correlation was found between the cross-tabulated job satisfaction

measures and turnover intention. While 88.12% of extremely dissatisfied workers were planning to leave their organizations, 89.56% of extremely satisfied workers were not seeking opportunities outside their organizations. Frequencies and percentages are presented in Table 22.

Table 22.

Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention Cross Tabulation

Variable	Turnover Intention		Total
	No	Yes	
Job Satisfaction			
Extremely Dissatisfied	22 (1.15%)	89 (12.82%)	101
Somewhat Dissatisfied	199 (10.42%)	193 (27.81%)	392
Somewhat Satisfied	994 (52.04%)	331 (47.69%)	1325
Extremely Satisfied	695 (36.39%)	81 (11.67%)	776
Total	1910 (100.00%)	694 (100.00%)	2604

Note. Due to rounding error, percentages may not sum to 100%.

Research Questions 5a Controlling for Age

When the model was controlled for the effect of age, the regression model was significant, $B = -0.02$, $OR = 0.98$, $p < .001$, indicating that a one-unit increase in age decrease the odds of observing the yes category of turnover intention by approximately 2.35%. Including age, as a covariate, along with the predictors, structural empowerment, and job satisfaction, in the second regression model, increased the original model's variance from 20% to 21.6%. The Hosmer & Lemeshow test result revealed the model remained at a non-significant Chi-Square level, $p = .745$, indicating continued adequate fit of the model while controlling for age. To estimate the validation of the model, the overall percentage accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity were compared. The original model without age, indicated an accuracy rate percentage correct

with 77.3% of cases correctly predicted, with 31.4% sensitivity, and 93.8%. There was an increase of 1%, from the original model, with a slight increase in the original model's sensitivity level of 29.3% and 93.4% specificity. A crosstabulation analysis of age and turnover intention. The observations of age of CNAs who were likely to leave their jobs (the Yes category) had an average of 34.08. The observations of age of CNAs who were not likely to leave (the No category) their jobs had an average of 37.64. Summary statistics of these findings are in Table 23.

Table 23.

Summary Statistics Table for Age by Turnover Intention Levels

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>SE_M</i>	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
AGE								
No	37.64	12.94	1910	0.30	16.00	65.00	0.30	-0.95
Yes	34.08	11.11	694	0.42	17.00	65.00	0.43	-0.84

It would also be beneficial to perform similar research including other age generation categories, that were not included in this study, to discover if there are considerable variations from what was reported in this research. There are few studies regarding age generational differences in nurse turnover intention. According to Koehler's findings (2022), there were notable differences in turnover intention across age generations. These findings support Nashwan et. al. study (2021), in which younger nurses were found to have higher turnover intention. However, Tolksdorf et al. (2022) was not unable to find a relationship between age and nurses' turnover intention in their findings, in which work environments during the COVID-19

pandemic and the SARS epic from 2002-2004, were compared. This knowledge may be beneficial to administrators and policymakers by targeting specific subpopulations and offering specific retention strategies and interventions.

Research Questions 5b, Controlling for Citizenship and Turnover Intention

For this study, the most frequently observed category of citizenship within the No category of turnover intention was U.S. Citizen ($n = 1,792, 93.82\%$). The most frequently observed category of *citizenship* within the Yes category of turnover intention was U.S. Citizen ($n = 642, 92.51\%$). However, both demographics were found to not likely leave their organizations when it came to turnover intention frequencies. Frequencies and percentages are presented in Table 24. These results aligned with the findings of Khatutsky et al. (2012), in which citizenship status, personal characteristics, and job satisfaction characteristics were explanatory variables in their multivariable logistic regression, conducted to better understand the relationship between citizenship status and turnover intention. Their results revealed non-U.S. citizen status is related to a higher likelihood of CNAs leaving their jobs within a year, even while considering the other factors in the model (Khatutsky et al., 2012).

Table 24.*Citizenship Status and Turnover Intention*

Variable	Turnover Intention	
	No	Yes
Citizenship		
Non-U.S. Citizen	118 (6.18%)	52 (7.49%)
U.S. Citizen	1792 (93.82%)	642 (92.51%)
Total	1910 (100.00%)	694 (100.00%)

Implications**Theoretical implications**

Empowerment has been discussed in multiple frameworks within the nursing literature. However, Kanter's Structural Empowerment theory continues to be the most utilized theoretical framework (Chunfeng & Zhou, 2009; Conger & Kanungo, 1988; Larkin, 2008; Laschinger et al., 2001; Laschinger et al., 2010). Because nursing assistants work in groups or teams to achieve their organization's mission, a nursing theory of group empowerment was ideal to guide this research. The theory was created from within a nursing conceptual framework and intended to support nursing work teams and groups to evaluate and enhance their teamwork and structural empowerment.

Kanter's structural empowerment theory focused on the organization and the work environment instead of the individual. This theory imparts the foundational premises that an individual must have access to structural components for the business to thrive. These components include support, resources, information, and opportunity. As these structural determinants are provided in the organization, the organization becomes successful because the

employees are more satisfied and committed to the company's goals due to the components, they have that support their role. Kanter's theory was used to guide this research using this framework to analyze items from the work environment, job satisfaction, and supervisor/management sections of the 2004 NNAS instrument. Access to opportunity, support, information, and structural empowerment (overall), were all found to have a statistically significant relationship with the CNA's turnover intention. These findings align with prior studies that have used this framework to link the concept of structural empowerment to several measurements such as burnout, engagement, incivility, intent to stay, job satisfaction, job tension, organizational trust, productivity, retention, work effectiveness, work quality (Cowden & Cummings, 2012; Laschinger, 2008; Lee, 2008; McDonald et al., 2010; Stein & Kanter, 1993; Young-Ritchie et al., 2009).

Applications to Professional Practice

Providing quality care in skilled nursing facilities is continuously growing and demanding. As Americans continue to live longer, delivering exceptional quality patient care necessitates a consistent, reliable, and empowered workforce. CNAs have a critical vital role in the healthcare delivery system, especially in the long-term care sector, for which patient care, safety, and satisfaction are critical. The findings of this research may support the decision makers and other members of skilled-care facility senior leadership in concentrating on strategies that will enable them to recruit and retain highly skilled and highly experienced CNAs, particularly

where there is a high demand and continuous lack of CNAs (Gandhi et al., 2021). The enhanced recruitment and retention of CNAs could allow facilities to see decreased recruiting, hiring, and onboarding budgets, better retention of organizational knowledge, skills, and experience, offer patients better quality care, safe environments, and improved patient care outcomes.

Practical implications

The results contributed a significant description regarding the differences in demographic characteristics can affect the workplace environment and organizational behaviors of direct care workers like CNAs. Structural empowerment components aligned with Kanter's Structural Empowerment theory (access to opportunity, support, resources, and information), overall structural empowerment and job satisfaction were accessed as predictors of turnover intention outcomes. These measurements compared the outcomes amongst age generation and citizenship status to reveal how each subset may be affected differently in their work environments (Berridge et al., 2018; Gandhi et al., 2021; Giancardolo & Comparcini, 2013; Sloane et al., 2010). This vital information may equip nurse administrators and supervisors with the information needed to create successful hiring and retention strategic plans to help meet the growing demands and needs for long-term care (Gandhi et al., 2021).

Implications for Social Change

Based upon the findings of this study, one of the social implications was to support current research findings by informing healthcare organizations and policymakers of the urgent

need for training opportunities for nursing assistants. Workforce development is a critical component in the healthcare facilities' success in retaining staff (Lim, 2021; Randall et al., 2022). Examining the effect of wages and training on direct care workers (DCWs) turnover intention ($n = 7,311$), Kishida (2022) found the impact of wage increase and higher training opportunities were greater for DCWs, who were intending to switch jobs instead of leaving their occupations all together. With CNAs serving as the frontline in this care, improved recruitment and hiring strategies coupled with strong retention strategies will increase the workforce and the quality of care provided to patients.

Recommendations for Future Research

I recommend for this research be replicated with a more current data source to see if the findings would be comparable to the 2004 data. Reproducing research tests investigators' results and thus aiding to the knowledgebase. It also helps to serve as a critical indicator of the reliability of scientific research by providing results that might be consistent, offering more opportunities to further provide evidence to increase and strengthen the generalizability of the original study (Block & Kuckertz, 2018).

The cross-sectional data used in this study created limitations because it was collected during a single period. A longitudinal design, which is observational like a cross-sectional study, allows researchers the ability to detect changes in the characteristics and outcomes that cannot be produced using cross-sectional data.

In promoting diverse work environments, it is recommended to consider a national sample population, in which age generations combined with gender specific events, such as the generation specific findings revealed in Tei-Tominaga, Asakura, & Asakura's study of age and childbearing relationship in Japanese nurse turnover. They found a significant relationship (OR = 1.59, CI: 1.13–2.25) in nurses who were caring for children and intention to leave in Generation X nurses (nurses born between 1965 and 1979 (35–49 years old) (Tei-Tominaga et al., 2018).

Gender is not limited to binary identifications and consists of normally distributed demographics that aligns with current work environment demographics. Considering people of color make up most of the nursing assistant workforce (PHI, 2020), the sample population was unevenly distributed in race and gender. Increasing diversity equity and inclusion (DEI) efforts entails improving the age, ethnic, racial, gender, and practical representation in our labor workforce. In the U.S., adults who identify as members of the lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, questioning, or queer (LGBTQ⁺) community encompasses around 4.1% (an estimate of 10 million adults) of the general population (ANA Center for Ethics and Human Rights, 2018). The lack of knowledge and understanding of the distinctive needs of this population promotes continuing occupational health disparities and prejudices. It is imperative for the nursing industry to consider the needs of LGBTQ⁺ populations in the areas of policy, procedure, instruction, and research (ANA Center for Ethics and Human Rights, 2018).

Conclusion

Despite the limitations in this research and to the best of my knowledge, the current study is the first study to investigate the predictors of structural empowerment and its subscales, job satisfaction, citizenship, and intent to leave, among nursing assistants in a nationally representative sample of nursing homes using multilevel modeling. The study's findings substantiate the results of previous CNAs' job satisfaction and turnover studies (Giancardolo & Comparcini, 2013; Squires et al., 2015; Stone, et al., 2017). More studies are needed to evaluate the effectiveness of workforce development strategies. These efforts would ideally assist key decision makers and policymakers in determining the need to conduct more studies in this area of research. However, the high stress, in which the COVID-19 pandemic produced in healthcare workers, offering adequate work environments, benefits, and incentives, is essential in their recruitment and retention.

This study used 18-items from the 2004 NNAS to thoroughly investigate whether structurally empowered work environment encompassing access to opportunities, support, information, resources, and job satisfaction are associated with nursing assistant turnover intention. While overall structural empowerment was significantly associated with increased CNA turnover intention, only three of the four structural dimensions (perceived access to opportunity, support, and information) were found to be significantly linked to their turnover intention. Resources, the fourth dimension, was not found to be linked to their turnover intention.

According to Kanter's structural empowerment theory, the importance of structural empowerment is because of NAs having access to four organizational sources: opportunity, support, information, and resources, and with access to formal and informal power components. NA structural empowerment is critical in fostering effective work environments in which they can commit, and experience decreased turnover intention. While it has been found structural empowerment is related to turnover intention, studies have indicated job satisfaction is also related to turnover intention (Fragkos et al., 2020).

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Appendix A

Variables Codebook

Variables	Variable type	NNAS Variable	NNAS Variable description	Original Scale	Level of measurement	NNAS item #
Turnover intention	Criterion	TURNOVER INTENTION	Are you looking for another job?	0 = no 1 = yes	Dichotomous	H11

Structural empowerment

Access to opportunity	Predictor	CHALLEN	I am involved in challenging work.	1 = strongly disagree 2 = somewhat disagree	Ordinal	I1C
		NEWSKILL	I have a chance to gain new skills and knowledge on the job.	3 = somewhat agree 4 = strongly agree		I1D
		TRUSTED	I am trusted to make resident care decisions.			I1E
		TEAMWORK	I have the opportunity to work in teams			I1F
Access to support	Predictor	SUPACTS	Deals with NAs' complaints and concerns.	1 = strongly disagree 2 = somewhat disagree	Ordinal	F1C
		SUPOPEN	Is open to new and different ideas.	3 = somewhat agree 4 = strongly agree		F1D
		SUPADVAN	Is supportive of progress in NA's career.			F1E
		SUPHELP	Helps NA with job tasks when needed.			F1F
		SUPHEAR	Listens when NA is worried about resident's care.			F1G
		SUPTEAM	Supports NAs working in teams with			F1H

Access to resources	Predictor	ASKNA	How much time does NA have to provide ADLs to residents in a typical work week	1 = never, 2 = once in a while, 3 = sometimes, or 4 = frequently	Ordinal	I6
		ASKSTAFF	How much time does NA have to complete duties not related to residents		Ordinal	I7
Access to information	Predictor	SUPCLEAR	Provided clear instruction when assigned work.	1 = strongly disagree 2 = somewhat disagree 3 = somewhat agree 4 = strongly agree	Ordinal	F1A
		SUPTELLS	NA is told when doing a good job		Ordinal	F1J
Turnover Intention	Predictor variable	TURNOVER INTENTION	Is NA currently looking for different job, either as a NA or something else?	0 = no 1 = yes	Ordinal	H1
Citizenship status	Covariate variable	CITIZEN	Are you a citizen of the United States?	0 = no 1 = yes	Nominal	K8

Age	Covariate variable	AGE	16 – 64 65 = 65 and older	Ratio	Kb
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Appendix B

Means and standard deviation of each subscale and sum of the means of Structural Empowerment Instrument

Items	Mean	SD
Opportunity	3.39	0.60
I am involved in challenging work.	3.58	0.73
I have a chance to gain new skills and knowledge on the job.	3.22	0.95
I am trusted to make resident care decisions.	3.41	0.86
I have the opportunity to work in teams.	3.36	0.95
Support	3.27	.075
Deals with NAs' complaints and concerns.	3.12	1.04
Is open to new and different ideas.	3.31	0.93
Is supportive of progress in NA's career.	3.16	1.03
Helps NA with job tasks when needed.	3.07	1.11
Listens when NA is worried about resident's care.	3.56	0.80
Supports NAs working in teams with other health care workers.	3.41	0.87
Resources	2.60	0.72
How much time does NA have to provide ADLs to residents in a typical work week?	2.82	0.83
How much time does NA have to complete duties not related to residents?	2.38	0.87
Information	3.31	0.83
Provided clear instruction when assigned work.	3.46	0.85
NA is told when doing a good job	3.15	1.09
Overall Structural Empowerment	12.57	2.05

Appendix C

IRB APPROVAL

Office of Institutional Research Institutional Review Board

2200 East Germann Road Chandler, AZ 85286
Office: (714) 816-0366 ext. 2518 | Fax: (714) 226-9844

Memo

From Simcha Pollard, Ph.D.
Chair, Institutional Review Board of Trident College
Re: IRB approval IRB # 1186

Protocol and Study Information	
Date Submitted to IRB: Submitted 10/1/2020 Approval 10/12/2020	
Principal Investigator: Tamekia Evans	Research Advisor: Dr. Carlos Cardillo
Proposal Title: Four Dimensions of Structural Empowerment and Their Associations with Turnover Intention in Certified Nursing Assistants Employed in U.S. Nursing Homes in 2004”.	
Investigator Information	
Name: Tamekia Evans	Department: College of Health and Human Services
Co-Investigator	
Co-Investigator	

I am pleased to inform you that Trident University IRB has approved your project exempt. Exemption is based upon Research involves collection or study of anonymous survey data, which does not contain identifiers linked to human subjects (CFR 46.0101(b)(4)), which is being evaluated. You will need to upload your approval letter into the IRB Approval Folder in your 800 Drop Box. Please feel free to start your study at any time. Reapplication is not required in a year if the study is still being conducted.

Best wishes and good luck,

Simcha (Stephen) Pollard, Ph. D